

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SGGKGGKAGSAAK**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 87289: 1200.609848 from(601.312200,2+) intensity(43510.7890) scans(1394) rawscans(sn1394) rtinseconds(880.3948) index(83479)

Title: 979: Scan 1394 (rt=14.6732) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23968.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1200.6098

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

K4 : Acetyl (K)

K7 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 107 Expect: 1.4e-09

Matches : 38/132 fragment ions using 32 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S							13
2	187.0713	94.0393			169.0608	85.0340	G	1072.5746	536.7909	1055.5480	528.2776	1054.5640	527.7856	12
3	244.0928	122.5500			226.0822	113.5448	G	1015.5531	508.2802	998.5265	499.7669	997.5425	499.2749	11
4	414.1983	207.6028	397.1718	199.0895	396.1878	198.5975	K	958.5316	479.7694	941.5051	471.2562	940.5211	470.7642	10
5	471.2198	236.1135	454.1932	227.6003	453.2092	227.1082	G	788.4261	394.7167	771.3995	386.2034	770.4155	385.7114	9
6	528.2413	264.6243	511.2147	256.1110	510.2307	255.6190	G	731.4046	366.2060	714.3781	357.6927	713.3941	357.2007	8
7	698.3468	349.6770	681.3202	341.1638	680.3362	340.6717	K	674.3832	337.6952	657.3566	329.1819	656.3726	328.6899	7
8	769.3839	385.1956	752.3573	376.6823	751.3733	376.1903	A	504.2776	252.6425	487.2511	244.1292	486.2671	243.6372	6
9	826.4054	413.7063	809.3788	405.1930	808.3948	404.7010	G	433.2405	217.1239	416.2140	208.6106	415.2300	208.1186	5
10	913.4374	457.2223	896.4108	448.7091	895.4268	448.2170	S	376.2191	188.6132	359.1925	180.0999	358.2085	179.6079	4
11	984.4745	492.7409	967.4480	484.2276	966.4639	483.7356	A	289.1870	145.0972	272.1605	136.5839			3
12	1055.5116	528.2594	1038.4851	519.7462	1037.5011	519.2542	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2
13							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI BLAST search of [SGGKGGKAGSAAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
106.7	1200.6098	0.0000	SGGKGGKAGSAAK	Acetyl N-term, K4, K7 100.00%
16.9	1200.6098	0.0000	SGGKGGKAGSAAK	Acetyl N-term, K4, K13 0.00%
12.3	1200.6098	0.0000	NKERDEKAK	
10.9	1200.6155	-0.0057	ITFLTQKSK	
9.8	1200.6155	-0.0057	VKLTDFGTAK	
8.9	1200.6155	-0.0057	ITFLTQKSK	
8.8	1200.6155	-0.0057	IKLTDFGTAK	
8.7	1200.6155	-0.0056	TKYDKIAAK	
8.6	1200.6128	-0.0030	SHKARELPR	
8.3	1200.6071	0.0027	ENRGRREDR	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SGGKGGKAGSAAK**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 103322: 1280.576708 from(641.295630,2+) intensity(13638.3540) scans(1873) rawscans(sn1873) rtinseconds(1019.1969) index(42439)

Title: 1410: Scan 1873 (rt=16.9866) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23966.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1280.5762

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

K4 : Acetyl (K)

K7 : Acetyl (K)

S10 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 30 Expect: 0.012 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S							13
2	187.0713	94.0393			169.0608	85.0340	G	1152.5409	576.7741	1135.5143	568.2608	1134.5303	567.7688	12
3	244.0928	122.5500			226.0822	113.5448	G	1095.5194	548.2633	1078.4929	539.7501	1077.5089	539.2581	11
4	414.1983	207.6028	397.1718	199.0895	396.1878	198.5975	K	1038.4980	519.7526	1021.4714	511.2393	1020.4874	510.7473	10
5	471.2198	236.1135	454.1932	227.6003	453.2092	227.1082	G	868.3924	434.6999	851.3659	426.1866	850.3819	425.6946	9
6	528.2413	264.6243	511.2147	256.1110	510.2307	255.6190	G	811.3710	406.1891	794.3444	397.6758	793.3604	397.1838	8
7	698.3468	349.6770	681.3202	341.1638	680.3362	340.6717	K	754.3495	377.6784	737.3229	369.1651	736.3389	368.6731	7
8	769.3839	385.1956	752.3573	376.6823	751.3733	376.1903	A	584.2440	292.6256	567.2174	284.1123	566.2334	283.6203	6
9	826.4054	413.7063	809.3788	405.1930	808.3948	404.7010	G	513.2069	257.1071	496.1803	248.5938	495.1963	248.1018	5
10	993.4037	497.2055	976.3772	488.6922	975.3932	488.2002	S	456.1854	228.5963	439.1588	220.0831	438.1748	219.5911	4
11	1064.4408	532.7241	1047.4143	524.2108	1046.4303	523.7188	A	289.1870	145.0972	272.1605	136.5839			3
12	1135.4779	568.2426	1118.4514	559.7293	1117.4674	559.2373	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2
13							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SGGKGGKAGSAAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
29.9	1280.5762	0.0006	SGGKGGKAGSAAK	Acetyl N-term, K4, K7, Phospho S10; 97.44%
8.8	1280.5762	0.0006	SGGKGGKAGSAAK	Acetyl N-term, K4, K13, Phospho S10; 0.76%
8.8	1280.5762	0.0006	DKSONPASNGK	
8.6	1280.5802	-0.0035	NNKKSISYYG	
8.2	1280.5802	-0.0035	NNKKSISYYG	
8.2	1280.5818	-0.0051	KDKTSLFK	
8.0	1280.5802	-0.0035	SKYETHAPVK	
7.8	1280.5802	-0.0035	NNKKSISYYG	
6.7	1280.5802	-0.0035	NNKKSISYYG	
5.8	1280.5713	0.0054	RASKSSGKMK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **GGKAGSAAKASQSR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 121751: 1358.689128 from(680.351840,2+) intensity(8178.7710) scans(1265) rawscans(sn1265) rtinseconds(805.8807) index(214650)

Title: 912: Scan 1265 (rt=13.4313) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23658.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), zoom in, zoom out, search, 136.7 to 1198.45, zoom in, zoom out, back, forward.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1358.6902
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K3 : Acetyl (K)
 K9 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 66 Expect: 3.8e-06
 Matches : 20/140 fragment ions using 27 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	58.0287	29.5180					G							14
2	115.0502	58.0287					G	1302.6761	651.8417	1285.6495	643.3284	1284.6655	642.8364	13
3	285.1557	143.0815	268.1292	134.5682			K	1245.6546	623.3309	1228.6280	614.8177	1227.6440	614.3257	12
4	356.1928	178.6001	339.1663	170.0868			A	1075.5491	538.2782	1058.5225	529.7649	1057.5385	529.2729	11
5	413.2143	207.1108	396.1878	198.5975			G	1004.5119	502.7596	987.4854	494.2463	986.5014	493.7543	10
6	500.2463	250.6268	483.2198	242.1135	482.2358	241.6215	S	947.4905	474.2489	930.4639	465.7356	929.4799	465.2436	9
7	571.2835	286.1454	554.2569	277.6321	553.2729	277.1401	A	860.4585	430.7329	843.4319	422.2196	842.4479	421.7276	8
8	642.3206	321.6639	625.2940	313.1506	624.3100	312.6586	A	789.4213	395.2143	772.3948	386.7010	771.4108	386.2090	7
9	812.4261	406.7167	795.3995	398.2034	794.4155	397.7114	K	718.3842	359.6958	701.3577	351.1825	700.3737	350.6905	6
10	883.4632	442.2352	866.4367	433.7220	865.4526	433.2300	A	548.2787	274.6430	531.2522	266.1297	530.2681	265.6377	5
11	970.4952	485.7513	953.4687	477.2380	952.4847	476.7460	S	477.2416	239.1244	460.2150	230.6112	459.2310	230.1191	4
12	1098.5538	549.7805	1081.5273	541.2673	1080.5432	540.7753	Q	390.2096	195.6084	373.1830	187.0951	372.1990	186.6031	3
13	1185.5858	593.2966	1168.5593	584.7833	1167.5753	584.2913	S	262.1510	131.5791	245.1244	123.0659	244.1404	122.5738	2
14							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [GGKAGSAAKASQSR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
66.1	1358.6902	-0.0011	GGKAGSAAKASQSR
7.8	1358.6902	-0.0011	HSSTSRNLSNSK
7.6	1358.6902	-0.0011	RNNTRSDEPTK
7.4	1358.6830	0.0061	YIYNTNNSKSK
6.8	1358.6902	-0.0011	KRAAGSGESTPER
6.1	1358.6959	-0.0068	YILSQVKVSSR
5.9	1358.6959	-0.0067	VKAGTYSASRK
5.9	1358.6959	-0.0067	VKAGTYSASRK
4.3	1358.6959	-0.0067	KKYADISRSK
4.3	1358.6959	-0.0067	KKYADISRSK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SAKAGLTFPVGR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 95901: 1244.686948 from(623.350750,2+) intensity(44986.5390) scans(6109) rawscans(sn6109) rtinseconds(2261.7605) index(16970)

Title: 4901: Scan 6109 (rt=37.696) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23962.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1244.6877

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K3 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 74 Expect: 2.2e-06

Matches : 22/118 fragment ions using 19 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	88.0393	44.5233			70.0287	35.5180	S							12
2	159.0764	80.0418			141.0659	71.0366	A	1158.6630	579.8351	1141.6364	571.3218	1140.6524	570.8298	11
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	K	1087.6259	544.3166	1070.5993	535.8033	1069.6153	535.3113	10
4	400.2191	200.6132	383.1925	192.0999	382.2085	191.6079	A	917.5203	459.2638	900.4938	450.7505	899.5098	450.2585	9
5	457.2405	229.1239	440.2140	220.6106	439.2300	220.1186	G	846.4832	423.7452	829.4567	415.2320	828.4726	414.7400	8
6	570.3246	285.6659	553.2980	277.1527	552.3140	276.6606	L	789.4618	395.2345	772.4352	386.7212	771.4512	386.2292	7
7	671.3723	336.1898	654.3457	327.6765	653.3617	327.1845	T	676.3777	338.6925	659.3511	330.1792	658.3671	329.6872	6
8	818.4407	409.7240	801.4141	401.2107	800.4301	400.7187	F	575.3300	288.1686	558.3035	279.6554			5
9	915.4934	458.2504	898.4669	449.7371	897.4829	449.2451	P	428.2616	214.6344	411.2350	206.1212			4
10	1014.5619	507.7846	997.5353	499.2713	996.5513	498.7793	V	331.2088	166.1081	314.1823	157.5948			3
11	1071.5833	536.2953	1054.5568	527.7820	1053.5728	527.2900	G	232.1404	116.5738	215.1139	108.0606			2
12							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SAKAGLTFPVGR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
74.2	1244.6877	-0.0008	SAKAGLTFPVGR
13.0	1244.6911	-0.0041	KEGKIVNMER
10.6	1244.6877	-0.0008	KADQLYPGKR
10.6	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR
10.6	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR
10.2	1244.6911	-0.0041	EAKQIMRSVK
9.9	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR
9.9	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR
9.9	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR
9.9	1244.6837	0.0033	DKRDKEEKR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SAKAGLTFPVGR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 90615: 1216.692042 from(406.571290,3+) intensity(48575.9300) scans(3521) rawscans(sn3521) rtinseconds(1610.1544) index(2673)

Title: 2674: Scan 3521 (rt=26.8359) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23662.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 109.95 to 890.33

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1216.6928

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K3 : Methyl (K)

Ions Score: 20 Expect: 0.71

Matches : 12/118 fragment ions using 24 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	88.0393	44.5233			70.0287	35.5180	S							12
2	159.0764	80.0418			141.0659	71.0366	A	1130.6681	565.8377	1113.6415	557.3244	1112.6575	556.8324	11
3	301.1870	151.0972	284.1605	142.5839	283.1765	142.0919	K	1059.6309	530.3191	1042.6044	521.8058	1041.6204	521.3138	10
4	372.2241	186.6157	355.1976	178.1024	354.2136	177.6104	A	917.5203	459.2638	900.4938	450.7505	899.5098	450.2585	9
5	429.2456	215.1264	412.2191	206.6132	411.2350	206.1212	G	846.4832	423.7452	829.4567	415.2320	828.4726	414.7400	8
6	542.3297	271.6685	525.3031	263.1552	524.3191	262.6632	L	789.4618	395.2345	772.4352	386.7212	771.4512	386.2292	7
7	643.3774	322.1923	626.3508	313.6790	625.3668	313.1870	T	676.3777	338.6925	659.3511	330.1792	658.3671	329.6872	6
8	790.4458	395.7265	773.4192	387.2132	772.4352	386.7212	F	575.3300	288.1686	558.3035	279.6554			5
9	887.4985	444.2529	870.4720	435.7396	869.4880	435.2476	P	428.2616	214.6344	411.2350	206.1212			4
10	986.5669	493.7871	969.5404	485.2738	968.5564	484.7818	V	331.2088	166.1081	314.1823	157.5948			3
11	1043.5884	522.2978	1026.5619	513.7846	1025.5778	513.2926	G	232.1404	116.5738	215.1139	108.0606			2
12							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SAKAGLTFPVGR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
20.3	1216.6928	-0.0008	SAKAGLTFPVGR
17.6	1216.6962	-0.0041	DAKVKMGGTVR
12.9	1216.6928	-0.0007	ASINSKFAGPR
10.8	1216.6896	0.0024	TMRMNRPK
10.8	1216.6896	0.0024	TMRMNRPK
10.8	1216.6896	0.0024	TMRMNRPK
9.7	1216.6961	-0.0041	LGEKEGKRMK
9.7	1216.6961	-0.0041	LGEKEGKRMK
9.7	1216.6962	-0.0041	LGEKEGKRMK
8.5	1216.6927	-0.0007	KEKFRKQK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **AGLTFPVGR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 33322: 930.527928 from(466.271240,2+) intensity(27740.6410) scans(6393) rawscans(sn6393)

rtinseconds(2137.2181) index(247569)

Title: 5368: Scan 6393 (rt=35.6203) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23976.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen 74.11 to 790.26

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 930.5287

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

R9 : Methyl (R)

Ions Score: 30 **Expect:** 0.08 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{***}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258			A							9
2	129.0659	65.0366			G	860.4989	430.7531	843.4723	422.2398	842.4883	421.7478	8
3	242.1499	121.5786			L	803.4774	402.2423	786.4509	393.7291	785.4668	393.2371	7
4	343.1976	172.1024	325.1870	163.0972	T	690.3933	345.7003	673.3668	337.1870	672.3828	336.6950	6
5	490.2660	245.6366	472.2554	236.6314	F	589.3457	295.1765	572.3191	286.6632			5
6	587.3188	294.1630	569.3082	285.1577	P	442.2772	221.6423	425.2507	213.1290			4
7	686.3872	343.6972	668.3766	334.6920	V	345.2245	173.1159	328.1979	164.6026			3
8	743.4087	372.2080	725.3981	363.2027	G	246.1561	123.5817	229.1295	115.0684			2
9					R	189.1346	95.0709	172.1081	86.5577			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [AGLTFPVGR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
29.6	930.5287	-0.0008	AGLTFPVGR
18.2	930.5287	-0.0007	AREFAAPK
15.5	930.5247	0.0033	RVSNOTGK
13.3	930.5246	0.0033	IKTREER
10.4	930.5320	-0.0041	KLELLCR
9.7	930.5287	-0.0008	SLKVEWR
7.9	930.5320	-0.0041	MKINVSR
7.2	930.5287	-0.0007	TKAHNYK
7.2	930.5246	0.0033	LASASROAK
7.2	930.5247	0.0033	GRVTNSNK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **AGLTFPVGR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 36238: 944.543888 from(473.279220,2+) intensity(121521.2500) scans(7942) rawscans(sn7942)

rtinseconds(2760.6603) index(220216)

Title: 6478: Scan 7942 (rt=46.011) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23658.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, zoom reset, 97.21 to 804.38 (m/z range), zoom in, right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 944.5444

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

R9 : Dimethyl (R)

Ions Score: 45 Expect: 0.0025

Matches : 13/64 fragment ions using 13 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258			A							9
2	129.0659	65.0366			G	874.5145	437.7609	857.4880	429.2476	856.5040	428.7556	8
3	242.1499	121.5786			L	817.4931	409.2502	800.4665	400.7369	799.4825	400.2449	7
4	343.1976	172.1024	325.1870	163.0972	T	704.4090	352.7081	687.3824	344.1949	686.3984	343.7028	6
5	490.2660	245.6366	472.2554	236.6314	F	603.3613	302.1843	586.3348	293.6710			5
6	587.3188	294.1630	569.3082	285.1577	P	456.2929	228.6501	439.2663	220.1368			4
7	686.3872	343.6972	668.3766	334.6920	V	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104			3
8	743.4087	372.2080	725.3981	363.2027	G	260.1717	130.5895	243.1452	122.0762			2
9					R	203.1503	102.0788	186.1237	93.5655			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [AGLTFPVGR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
45.4	944.5444	-0.0005	AGLTFPVGR
17.0	944.5477	-0.0038	IKDVMRK
15.8	944.5443	-0.0004	NDLFPRK
15.8	944.5443	-0.0005	NDLFPRK
14.6	944.5403	0.0036	IKTREER
14.6	944.5403	0.0036	IKTREER
13.9	944.5484	-0.0045	KWFIGPK
12.3	944.5477	-0.0038	RAIEMALK
12.0	944.5403	0.0036	DGRKOSLK
10.9	944.5477	-0.0038	KIKCNAK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **HLQLAIR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 17771: 849.518228 from(425.766390,2+) intensity(133018.1600) scans(3492) rawscans(sn3492) rtinseconds(1529.9571) index(43751)

Title: 2722: Scan 3492 (rt=25.4993) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23966.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, zoom reset, input field '75.21 to 813.42', zoom in, right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 849.5184

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Ions Score: 61 **Expect:** 1.9e-05

Matches : 11/44 fragment ions using 15 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ⁺⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ⁺⁺⁺	#
1	138.0662	69.5367			H					7
2	251.1503	126.0788			L	713.4668	357.2371	696.4403	348.7238	6
3	379.2088	190.1081	362.1823	181.5948	Q	600.3828	300.6950	583.3562	292.1817	5
4	492.2929	246.6501	475.2663	238.1368	L	472.3242	236.6657	455.2976	228.1525	4
5	563.3300	282.1686	546.3035	273.6554	A	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104	3
6	676.4141	338.7107	659.3875	330.1974	I	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919	2
7					R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498	1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [HLQLAIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
60.9	849.5184	-0.0002	HLQLAIR
30.4	849.5184	-0.0002	SYKRLR
23.3	849.5184	-0.0002	SYKRLR
17.9	849.5184	-0.0002	HLARKK
17.9	849.5185	-0.0002	HLIQGLR
17.9	849.5184	-0.0002	HLKAKR
17.7	849.5184	-0.0002	SYKRLR
16.1	849.5185	-0.0002	HLPVKSR
11.3	849.5184	-0.0002	IQHALLR
11.3	849.5184	-0.0002	KYSRIR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **HLQLAIR**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 23351: 877.549588 from(439.782070,2+) intensity(36232.1130) scans(4122) rawscans(sn4122)

rtinseconds(1641.3617) index(15328)

Title: 3259: Scan 4122 (rt=27.356) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23962.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Search Back Forward 78.11 to 841.52

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 877.5497

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

R7 : Dimethyl (R)

Ions Score: 21 Expect: 0.13 [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{***}	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{***}	#
1	138.0662	69.5367			H					7
2	251.1503	126.0788			L	741.4981	371.2527	724.4716	362.7394	6
3	379.2088	190.1081	362.1823	181.5948	Q	628.4141	314.7107	611.3875	306.1974	5
4	492.2929	246.6501	475.2663	238.1368	L	500.3555	250.6814	483.3289	242.1681	4
5	563.3300	282.1686	546.3035	273.6554	A	387.2714	194.1394	370.2449	185.6261	3
6	676.4141	338.7107	659.3875	330.1974	I	316.2343	158.6208	299.2078	150.1075	2
7					R	203.1503	102.0788	186.1237	93.5655	1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [HLQLAIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
20.9	877.5497	-0.0002	HLQLAIR
10.7	877.5498	-0.0002	HLGLRVK
10.7	877.5497	-0.0001	HLKKIR
9.4	877.5497	-0.0001	SYKRLR
9.4	877.5497	-0.0002	HLAKVLR
9.4	877.5497	-0.0002	HLIKLGR
9.4	877.5498	-0.0002	HLPVKS R
9.4	877.5498	-0.0002	HLPVKS R
9.4	877.5498	-0.0002	HLPVKS R
2.4	877.5497	-0.0001	LHKRLK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **NDDELNKLKLLGNVTIAQGGVLPNIHQNLK**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 335832: 3278.761136 from(820.697560,4+) intensity(4808.7051) scans(15077) rawscans(sn15077) rtinseconds(4689.7181) index(24613)

Title: 12544: Scan 15077 (rt=78.162) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23962.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 3278.7623
Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C)
Variable modifications: K7 : Acetyl (K)
Ions Score: 33 Expect: 0.026
Matches : 32/312 fragment ions using 47 most intense peaks

Table with 14 columns: #, b, b++, b*, b*+, b0, b0++, Seq., y, y++, y*, y*+, y0, y0+, #. Contains 21 rows of peptide fragment data.

22	2318.1987	1159.6030	2301.1721	1151.0897	2300.1881	1150.5977	N	1076.6211	538.8142	1059.5946	530.3009			9
23	2431.2827	1216.1450	2414.2562	1207.6317	2413.2722	1207.1397	I	962.5782	481.7927	945.5516	473.2795			8
24	2568.3416	1284.6745	2551.3151	1276.1612	2550.3311	1275.6692	H	849.4941	425.2507	832.4676	416.7374			7
25	2696.4002	1348.7037	2679.3737	1340.1905	2678.3897	1339.6985	Q	712.4352	356.7212	695.4087	348.2080			6
26	2810.4431	1405.7252	2793.4166	1397.2119	2792.4326	1396.7199	N	584.3766	292.6919	567.3501	284.1787			5
27	2923.5272	1462.2672	2906.5007	1453.7540	2905.5166	1453.2620	L	470.3337	235.6705	453.3071	227.1572			4
28	3036.6113	1518.8093	3019.5847	1510.2960	3018.6007	1509.8040	L	357.2496	179.1285	340.2231	170.6152			3
29	3133.6640	1567.3357	3116.6375	1558.8224	3115.6535	1558.3304	P	244.1656	122.5864	227.1390	114.0731			2
30							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI BLAST search of [NDDELNKLLGNVTIAQGGVLPNIHONLLPK](#)
 (Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)
 Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
33.3	3278.7623	-0.0011	NDDELNKLLGNVTIAQGGVLPNIHONLLPK
15.8	3278.7686	-0.0075	STNKSKMVNTGKNYILGGHNKVKNNSR
15.5	3278.7649	-0.0038	GKLVDLLSDEGIVNSAGDTLTVKKNYLYK
15.1	3278.7580	0.0031	EFLKGIGSKKNPVFHRVVKEENIYNK
15.1	3278.7721	-0.0110	DKISQKIINKEINLPDPNSNOGESTTKK
15.1	3278.7721	-0.0110	DKISQKIINKEINLPDPNSNOGESTTKK
15.1	3278.7721	-0.0110	DKISQKIINKEINLPDPNSNOGESTTKK
15.1	3278.7721	-0.0110	DKISQKIINKEINLPDPNSNOGESTTKK
15.0	3278.7516	0.0095	DSALVPAEALISLAKRRVAVARTDGLKK
15.0	3278.7516	0.0095	DSALVPAEALISLAKRRVAVARTDGLKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **ATKASQEL**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 24757: 888.455068 from(445.234810,2+) intensity(67322.0390) scans(3024) rawscans(sn3024) rtinseconds(1271.5559) index(98128)

Title: 2380: Scan 3024 (rt=21.1926) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23970.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 888.4552

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K3 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 43 **Expect:** 0.00058

Matches : 18/72 fragment ions using 18 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							8
2	173.0921	87.0497			155.0815	78.0444	T	818.4254	409.7164	801.3989	401.2031	800.4149	400.7111	7
3	343.1976	172.1024	326.1710	163.5892	325.1870	163.0972	K	717.3777	359.1925	700.3512	350.6792	699.3672	350.1872	6
4	414.2347	207.6210	397.2082	199.1077	396.2241	198.6157	A	547.2722	274.1397	530.2457	265.6265	529.2617	265.1345	5
5	501.2667	251.1370	484.2402	242.6237	483.2562	242.1317	S	476.2351	238.6212	459.2086	230.1079	458.2245	229.6159	4
6	629.3253	315.1663	612.2988	306.6530	611.3148	306.1610	Q	389.2031	195.1052	372.1765	186.5919	371.1925	186.0999	3
7	758.3679	379.6876	741.3414	371.1743	740.3573	370.6823	E	261.1445	131.0759			243.1339	122.0706	2
8							L	132.1019	66.5546					1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [ATKASQEL](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
42.6	888.4552	-0.0002	ATKASQEL
42.6	888.4552	-0.0002	TAKASQEL
7.6	888.4552	-0.0002	IGDOSISK
5.5	888.4552	-0.0001	ENKSLSK
5.5	888.4552	-0.0002	TADTSKPK
5.1	888.4561	-0.0010	MPV LGMNK
4.2	888.4552	-0.0001	EEKSINK
4.2	888.4552	-0.0001	EKEAENK
4.2	888.4552	-0.0002	SLDLAENK
2.7	888.4552	-0.0002	NVEADSIK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **ATKASQEL**

Found in **H2A1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P04911|H2A1_YEAST Histone H2A.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTA1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 42313: 968.421508 from(485.218030,2+) intensity(33457.2150) scans(2082) rawscans(sn2082) rtinseconds(1089.4626) index(84057)

Title: 1557: Scan 2082 (rt=18.1577) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23968.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

?
 to

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 968.4216

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K3 : Acetyl (K)

S5 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 21 **Expect:** 0.088 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							8
2	173.0921	87.0497			155.0815	78.0444	T	898.3918	449.6995	881.3652	441.1862	880.3812	440.6942	7
3	343.1976	172.1024	326.1710	163.5892	325.1870	163.0972	K	797.3441	399.1757	780.3175	390.6624	779.3335	390.1704	6
4	414.2347	207.6210	397.2082	199.1077	396.2241	198.6157	A	627.2385	314.1229	610.2120	305.6096	609.2280	305.1176	5
5	581.2331	291.1202	564.2065	282.6069	563.2225	282.1149	S	556.2014	278.6044	539.1749	270.0911	538.1909	269.5991	4
6	709.2916	355.1495	692.2651	346.6362	691.2811	346.1442	Q	389.2031	195.1052	372.1765	186.5919	371.1925	186.0999	3
7	838.3342	419.6708	821.3077	411.1575	820.3237	410.6655	E	261.1445	131.0759			243.1339	122.0706	2
8							L	132.1019	66.5546					1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [ATKASQEL](#)
 (Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)
 Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
21.3	968.4216	-0.0000	ATKASQEL
21.3	968.4216	-0.0000	TAKASQEL
9.4	968.4216	-0.0001	NDLVSATK
8.0	968.4216	-0.0001	DVQDIGSK
7.8	968.4216	-0.0000	ATGLAAESK
7.4	968.4216	-0.0001	NVEADSIK
6.2	968.4216	-0.0000	ATKASQEL
6.2	968.4216	-0.0000	TAKASQEL
5.8	968.4191	0.0024	MPHSTFK
4.4	968.4216	-0.0000	KEIDSNK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SAKAEKKPASK**

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 100881: 1269.692188 from(635.853370,2+) intensity(69641.7970) scans(1517) rawscans(sn1517) rtinseconds(832.1771) index(258719)

Title: 1200: Scan 1517 (rt=13.8696) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23664.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 109.94 to 1242.58

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1269.6928

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

K3 : Acetyl (K)

K6 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 54 Expect: 0.00025

Matches : 25/114 fragment ions using 29 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S							11
2	201.0870	101.0471			183.0764	92.0418	A	1141.6576	571.3324	1124.6310	562.8191	1123.6470	562.3271	10
3	371.1925	186.0999	354.1660	177.5866	353.1819	177.0946	K	1070.6204	535.8139	1053.5939	527.3006	1052.6099	526.8086	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	A	900.5149	450.7611	883.4884	442.2478	882.5043	441.7558	8
5	571.2722	286.1397	554.2457	277.6265	553.2617	277.1345	E	829.4778	415.2425	812.4512	406.7293	811.4672	406.2373	7
6	741.3777	371.1925	724.3512	362.6792	723.3672	362.1872	K	700.4352	350.7212	683.4087	342.2080	682.4246	341.7160	6
7	869.4727	435.2400	852.4462	426.7267	851.4621	426.2347	K	530.3297	265.6685	513.3031	257.1552	512.3191	256.6632	5
8	966.5255	483.7664	949.4989	475.2531	948.5149	474.7611	P	402.2347	201.6210	385.2082	193.1077	384.2241	192.6157	4
9	1037.5626	519.2849	1020.5360	510.7717	1019.5520	510.2796	A	305.1819	153.0946	288.1554	144.5813	287.1714	144.0893	3
10	1124.5946	562.8009	1107.5681	554.2877	1106.5841	553.7957	S	234.1448	117.5761	217.1183	109.0628	216.1343	108.5708	2
11							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SAKAEKKPASK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
53.8	1269.6928	-0.0006	SAKAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K3, K6 96.32%
39.6	1269.6928	-0.0006	SAKAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K3, K7 3.64%
16.3	1269.6928	-0.0006	SAKAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K3, K11 0.02%
14.5	1269.6945	-0.0023	TIKSELSKSK	
12.8	1269.6928	-0.0006	EKAEAAKAKAK	
12.7	1269.6929	-0.0007	QLEDIIVQNGK	
10.9	1269.6958	-0.0036	ERKSLFRAK	
10.9	1269.6958	-0.0036	ERKSLFRAK	
10.9	1269.6958	-0.0036	ERKSLFRAK	
10.0	1269.6880	0.0042	KACKNSTKK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SAKAEEKK**PASK

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 100872: 1269.691408 from(635.852980,2+) intensity(17760.9200) scans(1423) rawscans(sn1423) rtinseconds(814.7078) index(156851)

Title: 1083: Scan 1423 (rt=13.5785) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23670.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1269.6928

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

K6 : Acetyl (K)

K7 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 31 Expect: 0.086

Matches : 12/114 fragment ions using 28 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S							11
2	201.0870	101.0471			183.0764	92.0418	A	1141.6576	571.3324	1124.6310	562.8191	1123.6470	562.3271	10
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	K	1070.6204	535.8139	1053.5939	527.3006	1052.6099	526.8086	9
4	400.2191	200.6132	383.1925	192.0999	382.2085	191.6079	A	942.5255	471.7664	925.4989	463.2531	924.5149	462.7611	8
5	529.2617	265.1345	512.2351	256.6212	511.2511	256.1292	E	871.4884	436.2478	854.4618	427.7345	853.4778	427.2425	7
6	699.3672	350.1872	682.3406	341.6740	681.3566	341.1819	K	742.4458	371.7265	725.4192	363.2132	724.4352	362.7212	6
7	869.4727	435.2400	852.4462	426.7267	851.4621	426.2347	K	572.3402	286.6738	555.3137	278.1605	554.3297	277.6685	5
8	966.5255	483.7664	949.4989	475.2531	948.5149	474.7611	P	402.2347	201.6210	385.2082	193.1077	384.2241	192.6157	4
9	1037.5626	519.2849	1020.5360	510.7717	1019.5520	510.2796	A	305.1819	153.0946	288.1554	144.5813	287.1714	144.0893	3
10	1124.5946	562.8009	1107.5681	554.2877	1106.5841	553.7957	S	234.1448	117.5761	217.1183	109.0628	216.1343	108.5708	2
11							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SAKAEKKPASK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
30.8	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK
18.3	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK
12.1	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK
10.7	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK
5.2	1269.6928	-0.0014	AEKNKTENPK
5.1	1269.6928	-0.0014	AEKNKTENPK
5.0	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK
4.1	1269.6928	-0.0014	AEKNKTENPK
4.0	1269.6928	-0.0014	AEKNKTENPK
4.0	1269.6928	-0.0014	SAKAEKKPASK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SSAAEKKPASK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 91952: 1228.626128 from(615.320340,2+) intensity(18453.7660) scans(2442) rawscans(sn2442) rtinseconds(1068.117) index(319253)

Title: 1970: Scan 2442 (rt=17.802) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23982.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

134.22 to 1183.53

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1228.6299

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

K6 : Acetyl (K)

K7 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 59 Expect: 8.6e-05

Matches : 11/108 fragment ions using 9 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S							11
2	217.0819	109.0446			199.0713	100.0393	S	1100.5946	550.8009	1083.5681	542.2877	1082.5841	541.7957	10
3	288.1190	144.5631			270.1084	135.5579	A	1013.5626	507.2849	996.5360	498.7717	995.5520	498.2796	9
4	359.1561	180.0817			341.1456	171.0764	A	942.5255	471.7664	925.4989	463.2531	924.5149	462.7611	8
5	488.1987	244.6030			470.1882	235.5977	E	871.4884	436.2478	854.4618	427.7345	853.4778	427.2425	7
6	658.3042	329.6558	641.2777	321.1425	640.2937	320.6505	K	742.4458	371.7265	725.4192	363.2132	724.4352	362.7212	6
7	828.4098	414.7085	811.3832	406.1953	810.3992	405.7032	K	572.3402	286.6738	555.3137	278.1605	554.3297	277.6685	5
8	925.4625	463.2349	908.4360	454.7216	907.4520	454.2296	P	402.2347	201.6210	385.2082	193.1077	384.2241	192.6157	4
9	996.4997	498.7535	979.4731	490.2402	978.4891	489.7482	A	305.1819	153.0946	288.1554	144.5813	287.1714	144.0893	3
10	1083.5317	542.2695	1066.5051	533.7562	1065.5211	533.2642	S	234.1448	117.5761	217.1183	109.0628	216.1343	108.5708	2
11							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SSAAEKKPASK](#)
 (Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)
 Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
59.3	1228.6299	-0.0037	SSAAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K6, K7 99.98%
20.2	1228.6299	-0.0037	SSAAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K6, K11 0.01%
18.8	1228.6216	0.0045	SAYRKLSVK	
13.5	1228.6233	0.0028	ISSPLAKAVK	
11.8	1228.6299	-0.0037	SSAAEKKPASK	Acetyl N-term, K7, K11 0.00%
11.3	1228.6299	-0.0038	DDNGKEKKK	
11.3	1228.6299	-0.0038	DDNGKEKKK	
11.3	1228.6299	-0.0038	DDNGKEKKK	
11.1	1228.6308	-0.0046	QMKAPKMPDK	
10.9	1228.6217	0.0045	RDEKVFSAK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **AEKKPASKAPAEKKPAAK**

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 228300: 1975.109502 from(659.377110,3+) intensity(22931.4470) scans(897) rawscans(sn897) rtinseconds(650.1091) index(200073)

Title: 668: Scan 897 (rt=10.8352) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23958.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 118.17 to 1192.7

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1975.1101

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K4 : Acetyl (K)

K8 : Acetyl (K)

K13 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 60 Expect: 0.0003

Matches : 31/186 fragment ions using 37 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							18
2	201.0870	101.0471			183.0764	92.0418	E	1905.0804	953.0438	1888.0538	944.5306	1887.0698	944.0386	17
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	K	1776.0378	888.5225	1759.0112	880.0093	1758.0272	879.5173	16
4	499.2875	250.1474	482.2609	241.6341	481.2769	241.1421	K	1647.9428	824.4751	1630.9163	815.9618	1629.9323	815.4698	15
5	596.3402	298.6738	579.3137	290.1605	578.3297	289.6685	P	1477.8373	739.4223	1460.8108	730.9090	1459.8267	730.4170	14
6	667.3774	334.1923	650.3508	325.6790	649.3668	325.1870	A	1380.7845	690.8959	1363.7580	682.3826	1362.7740	681.8906	13
7	754.4094	377.7083	737.3828	369.1951	736.3988	368.7030	S	1309.7474	655.3774	1292.7209	646.8641	1291.7369	646.3721	12
8	924.5149	462.7611	907.4884	454.2478	906.5043	453.7558	K	1222.7154	611.8613	1205.6889	603.3481	1204.7048	602.8561	11
9	995.5520	498.2796	978.5255	489.7664	977.5415	489.2744	A	1052.6099	526.8086	1035.5833	518.2953	1034.5993	517.8033	10
10	1092.6048	546.8060	1075.5782	538.2928	1074.5942	537.8007	P	981.5728	491.2900	964.5462	482.7767	963.5622	482.2847	9
11	1163.6419	582.3246	1146.6154	573.8113	1145.6313	573.3193	A	884.5200	442.7636	867.4934	434.2504	866.5094	433.7584	8
12	1292.6845	646.8459	1275.6579	638.3326	1274.6739	637.8406	E	813.4829	407.2451	796.4563	398.7318	795.4723	398.2398	7
13	1462.7900	731.8986	1445.7635	723.3854	1444.7795	722.8934	K	684.4403	342.7238	667.4137	334.2105			6
14	1590.8850	795.9461	1573.8584	787.4329	1572.8744	786.9408	K	514.3348	257.6710	497.3082	249.1577			5
15	1687.9377	844.4725	1670.9112	835.9592	1669.9272	835.4672	P	386.2398	193.6235	369.2132	185.1103			4
16	1758.9749	879.9911	1741.9483	871.4778	1740.9643	870.9858	A	289.1870	145.0972	272.1605	136.5839			3
17	1830.0120	915.5096	1812.9854	906.9964	1812.0014	906.5043	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2

18						K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1
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NCBI BLAST search of [AEKKPASKAPAEKKPAAK](#)
 (Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)
 Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
60.3	1975.1101	-0.0006	AEKKPASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K4, K8, K13 99.89%
29.0	1975.1003	0.0092	ERGQVKKVANKFNGFK	
27.2	1975.1101	-0.0006	AEKKPASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K3, K4, K18 0.05%
23.4	1975.1091	0.0004	NLKRRTGGVKNNASLK	
23.4	1975.1091	0.0004	NLKRRTGGVKNNASLK	
20.9	1975.1003	0.0092	ERGQVKKVANKFNGFK	
20.7	1975.1003	0.0092	ERGQVKKVANKFNGFK	
18.5	1975.1118	-0.0023	DIVSKNNAEKLILAKK	
18.5	1975.1118	-0.0023	DIVSKNNAEKLILAKK	
13.9	1975.1003	0.0092	ERGQVKKVANKFNGFK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KPASKAPAEKKPAAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 178665: 1684.889022 from(562.636950,3+) intensity(60246.8500) scans(988-1002) rawscans(sn988:sn1002) rtinseconds(709.4411-713.9901) index(54619)

Title: 714: Sum of 2 scans in range 988 (rt=11.824) to 1002 (rt=11.8998) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23666.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1684.8912
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 S4 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769
 K5 : Acetyl (K)
 K11 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 40 Expect: 0.0075
 Matches : 24/234 fragment ions using 30 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	129.1022	65.0548	112.0757	56.5415			K							15
2	226.1550	113.5811	209.1285	105.0679			P	1557.8036	779.4055	1540.7771	770.8922	1539.7931	770.4002	14
3	297.1921	149.0997	280.1656	140.5864			A	1460.7509	730.8791	1443.7243	722.3658	1442.7403	721.8738	13
4	464.1905	232.5989	447.1639	224.0856	446.1799	223.5936	S	1389.7138	695.3605	1372.6872	686.8472	1371.7032	686.3552	12
5	634.2960	317.6516	617.2695	309.1384	616.2854	308.6464	K	1222.7154	611.8613	1205.6889	603.3481	1204.7048	602.8561	11
6	705.3331	353.1702	688.3066	344.6569	687.3226	344.1649	A	1052.6099	526.8086	1035.5833	518.2953	1034.5993	517.8033	10
7	802.3859	401.6966	785.3593	393.1833	784.3753	392.6913	P	981.5728	491.2900	964.5462	482.7767	963.5622	482.2847	9
8	873.4230	437.2151	856.3964	428.7019	855.4124	428.2099	A	884.5200	442.7636	867.4934	434.2504	866.5094	433.7584	8
9	1002.4656	501.7364	985.4390	493.2232	984.4550	492.7312	E	813.4829	407.2451	796.4563	398.7318	795.4723	398.2398	7
10	1130.5606	565.7839	1113.5340	557.2706	1112.5500	556.7786	K	684.4403	342.7238	667.4137	334.2105			6
11	1300.6661	650.8367	1283.6395	642.3234	1282.6555	641.8314	K	556.3453	278.6763	539.3188	270.1630			5
12	1397.7188	699.3631	1380.6923	690.8498	1379.7083	690.3578	P	386.2398	193.6235	369.2132	185.1103			4
13	1468.7560	734.8816	1451.7294	726.3683	1450.7454	725.8763	A	289.1870	145.0972	272.1605	136.5839			3
14	1539.7931	770.4002	1522.7665	761.8869	1521.7825	761.3949	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2
15							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KPASKAPAEKKPAAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
39.8	1684.8912	-0.0022	KPASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K5, K11 69.31%
34.2	1684.8912	-0.0022	KPASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K5, K15 19.18%
31.4	1684.8912	-0.0022	KPASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K5, K10 9.88%
16.2	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	
13.8	1684.8807	0.0083	KRKSGSNSGTLRMK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KPASKAPAEKKPAAKK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 192337: 1775.028852 from(592.683560,3+) intensity(58053.7540) scans(667) rawscans(sn667) rtinseconds(590.3626) index(271782)

Title: 474: Scan 667 (rt=9.83938) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23960.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, right arrow, search bar (109.06 to 1251.71), magnifying glass (search), right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1775.0304
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K5 : Acetyl (K)
 K10 : Acetyl (K)
 K11 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 68 Expect: 3.2e-05
 Matches : 31/160 fragment ions using 39 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	129.1022	65.0548	112.0757	56.5415			K							16
2	226.1550	113.5811	209.1285	105.0679			P	1647.9428	824.4751	1630.9163	815.9618	1629.9323	815.4698	15
3	297.1921	149.0997	280.1656	140.5864			A	1550.8901	775.9487	1533.8635	767.4354	1532.8795	766.9434	14
4	384.2241	192.6157	367.1976	184.1024	366.2136	183.6104	S	1479.8530	740.4301	1462.8264	731.9168	1461.8424	731.4248	13
5	554.3297	277.6685	537.3031	269.1552	536.3191	268.6632	K	1392.8209	696.9141	1375.7944	688.4008	1374.8104	687.9088	12
6	625.3668	313.1870	608.3402	304.6738	607.3562	304.1817	A	1222.7154	611.8613	1205.6889	603.3481	1204.7048	602.8561	11
7	722.4196	361.7134	705.3930	353.2001	704.4090	352.7081	P	1151.6783	576.3428	1134.6517	567.8295	1133.6677	567.3375	10
8	793.4567	397.2320	776.4301	388.7187	775.4461	388.2267	A	1054.6255	527.8164	1037.5990	519.3031	1036.6150	518.8111	9
9	922.4993	461.7533	905.4727	453.2400	904.4887	452.7480	E	983.5884	492.2978	966.5619	483.7846	965.5778	483.2926	8
10	1092.6048	546.8060	1075.5782	538.2928	1074.5942	537.8007	K	854.5458	427.7765	837.5193	419.2633			7
11	1262.7103	631.8588	1245.6838	623.3455	1244.6997	622.8535	K	684.4403	342.7238	667.4137	334.2105			6
12	1359.7631	680.3852	1342.7365	671.8719	1341.7525	671.3799	P	514.3348	257.6710	497.3082	249.1577			5
13	1430.8002	715.9037	1413.7736	707.3905	1412.7896	706.8985	A	417.2820	209.1446	400.2554	200.6314			4
14	1501.8373	751.4223	1484.8108	742.9090	1483.8267	742.4170	A	346.2449	173.6261	329.2183	165.1128			3
15	1629.9323	815.4698	1612.9057	806.9565	1611.9217	806.4645	K	275.2078	138.1075	258.1812	129.5942			2
16							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KPASKAPAEEKKPAACK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
68.5	1775.0304	-0.0016	KPASKAPAEEKKPAACK
28.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
28.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
28.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
21.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
21.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
21.9	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
19.7	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
19.7	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK
19.7	1775.0377	-0.0089	SGVKRKRGTSSGSEKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **PASKAPAEKKPAAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 145204: 1476.829482 from(493.283770,3+) intensity(26094.0270) scans(850) rawscans(sn850) rtinseconds(636.1738) index(286713)

Title: 605: Scan 850 (rt=10.6029) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23978.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

? 47.16 to 1152.82

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1476.8300
Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
Variable modifications:
 K4 : Acetyl (K)
 K9 : Acetyl (K)
Ions Score: 70 **Expect:** 7.3e-06
Matches : 47/134 fragment ions using 61 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	98.0600	49.5337					P							14
2	169.0972	85.0522					A	1380.7845	690.8959	1363.7580	682.3826	1362.7740	681.8906	13
3	256.1292	128.5682			238.1186	119.5629	S	1309.7474	655.3774	1292.7209	646.8641	1291.7369	646.3721	12
4	426.2347	213.6210	409.2082	205.1077	408.2241	204.6157	K	1222.7154	611.8613	1205.6889	603.3481	1204.7048	602.8561	11
5	497.2718	249.1395	480.2453	240.6263	479.2613	240.1343	A	1052.6099	526.8086	1035.5833	518.2953	1034.5993	517.8033	10
6	594.3246	297.6659	577.2980	289.1527	576.3140	288.6606	P	981.5728	491.2900	964.5462	482.7767	963.5622	482.2847	9
7	665.3617	333.1845	648.3352	324.6712	647.3511	324.1792	A	884.5200	442.7636	867.4934	434.2504	866.5094	433.7584	8
8	794.4043	397.7058	777.3777	389.1925	776.3937	388.7005	E	813.4829	407.2451	796.4563	398.7318	795.4723	398.2398	7
9	964.5098	482.7585	947.4833	474.2453	946.4993	473.7533	K	684.4403	342.7238	667.4137	334.2105			6
10	1092.6048	546.8060	1075.5782	538.2928	1074.5942	537.8007	K	514.3348	257.6710	497.3082	249.1577			5
11	1189.6576	595.3324	1172.6310	586.8191	1171.6470	586.3271	P	386.2398	193.6235	369.2132	185.1103			4
12	1260.6947	630.8510	1243.6681	622.3377	1242.6841	621.8457	A	289.1870	145.0972	272.1605	136.5839			3
13	1331.7318	666.3695	1314.7052	657.8563	1313.7212	657.3642	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2
14							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [PASKAPAEKKPAAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
70.0	1476.8300	-0.0005	PASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K4, K9 85.52%
62.2	1476.8300	-0.0005	PASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K4, K10 14.46%
35.2	1476.8300	-0.0005	PASKAPAEKKPAAK	Acetyl K4, K14 0.03%
14.3	1476.8317	-0.0022	KVVVPSEPTKSK	
11.4	1476.8317	-0.0022	KVVVPSEPTKSK	
10.3	1476.8317	-0.0022	KVVVPSEPTKSK	
9.9	1476.8317	-0.0022	KVVVPSEPTKSK	
9.0	1476.8317	-0.0022	TGKPTKLSVQLK	
8.4	1476.8317	-0.0022	KVVVPSEPTKSK	
7.8	1476.8317	-0.0022	KKPAPTGSESCK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **PASKAPAEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK**

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c)
 GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 298122: 2466.296772 from(823.106200,3+) intensity(7859.2515) scans(2377) rawscans(sn2377) rtinseconds(1021.7702) index(288057)

Title: 1949: Scan 2377 (rt=17.0295) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23978.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 2466.2965
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K4 : Acetyl (K)
 K9 : Acetyl (K)
 K14 : Acetyl (K)
 K23 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 40 Expect: 0.0089
 Matches : 35/250 fragment ions using 69 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ⁺⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ⁺⁺⁺	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	98.0600	49.5337					P							23
2	169.0972	85.0522					A	2370.2511	1185.6292	2353.2245	1177.1159	2352.2405	1176.6239	22
3	256.1292	128.5682			238.1186	119.5629	S	2299.2140	1150.1106	2282.1874	1141.5974	2281.2034	1141.1053	21
4	426.2347	213.6210	409.2082	205.1077	408.2241	204.6157	K	2212.1820	1106.5946	2195.1554	1098.0813	2194.1714	1097.5893	20
5	497.2718	249.1395	480.2453	240.6263	479.2613	240.1343	A	2042.0764	1021.5419	2025.0499	1013.0286	2024.0659	1012.5366	19
6	594.3246	297.6659	577.2980	289.1527	576.3140	288.6606	P	1971.0393	986.0233	1954.0128	977.5100	1953.0287	977.0180	18
7	665.3617	333.1845	648.3352	324.6712	647.3511	324.1792	A	1873.9865	937.4969	1856.9600	928.9836	1855.9760	928.4916	17
8	794.4043	397.7058	777.3777	389.1925	776.3937	388.7005	E	1802.9494	901.9784	1785.9229	893.4651	1784.9389	892.9731	16
9	964.5098	482.7585	947.4833	474.2453	946.4993	473.7533	K	1673.9068	837.4571	1656.8803	828.9438	1655.8963	828.4518	15
10	1092.6048	546.8060	1075.5782	538.2928	1074.5942	537.8007	K	1503.8013	752.4043	1486.7748	743.8910	1485.7907	743.3990	14
11	1189.6576	595.3324	1172.6310	586.8191	1171.6470	586.3271	P	1375.7064	688.3568	1358.6798	679.8435	1357.6958	679.3515	13
12	1260.6947	630.8510	1243.6681	622.3377	1242.6841	621.8457	A	1278.6536	639.8304	1261.6270	631.3172	1260.6430	630.8251	12
13	1331.7318	666.3695	1314.7052	657.8563	1313.7212	657.3642	A	1207.6165	604.3119	1190.5899	595.7986	1189.6059	595.3066	11
14	1501.8373	751.4223	1484.8108	742.9090	1483.8267	742.4170	K	1136.5794	568.7933	1119.5528	560.2800	1118.5688	559.7880	10
15	1629.9323	815.4698	1612.9057	806.9565	1611.9217	806.4645	K	966.4738	483.7406	949.4473	475.2273	948.4633	474.7353	9
16	1730.9799	865.9936	1713.9534	857.4803	1712.9694	856.9883	T	838.3789	419.6931	821.3523	411.1798	820.3683	410.6878	8
17	1818.0120	909.5096	1800.9854	900.9964	1800.0014	900.5043	S	737.3312	369.1692	720.3046	360.6560	719.3206	360.1640	7
18	1919.0597	960.0335	1902.0331	951.5202	1901.0491	951.0282	T	650.2992	325.6532	633.2726	317.1399	632.2886	316.6479	6
19	2006.0917	1003.5495	1989.0651	995.0362	1988.0811	994.5442	S	549.2515	275.1294	532.2249	266.6161	531.2409	266.1241	5

20	2107.1394	1054.0733	2090.1128	1045.5600	2089.1288	1045.0680	T	462.2195	231.6134	445.1929	223.1001	444.2089	222.6081	4
21	2222.1663	1111.5868	2205.1398	1103.0735	2204.1557	1102.5815	D	361.1718	181.0895	344.1452	172.5763	343.1612	172.0842	3
22	2279.1878	1140.0975	2262.1612	1131.5842	2261.1772	1131.0922	G	246.1448	123.5761	229.1183	115.0628			2
23							K	189.1234	95.0653	172.0968	86.5520			1

NCBI BLAST search of [PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
39.5	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K14, K23 34.04%
38.8	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K15, K23 28.45%
35.3	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K14, K15 12.79%
32.8	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K10, K14, K15 7.23%
31.2	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K10, K14, K23 4.95%
28.9	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K10, K15, K23 2.94%
23.8	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K10, K23 0.91%
21.9	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K10, K15 0.58%
21.6	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K14, K15, K23 0.55%
19.8	2466.2965	0.0003	PASKAPAEEKKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K4, K9, K10, K14 0.36%

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE **Mascot Search Results**

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK**

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 231824: 1999.058502 from(667.360110,3+) intensity(52096.4650) scans(646) rawscans(sn646) rtinseconds(613.6208) index(54333)

Title: 428: Scan 646 (rt=10.227) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23666.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1999.0585
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K10 : Acetyl (K)
 K11 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 77 Expect: 1.9e-06
 Matches : 41/198 fragment ions using 42 most intense peaks (help)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							19
2	169.0972	85.0522					P	1929.0287	965.0180	1912.0022	956.5047	1911.0182	956.0127	18
3	240.1343	120.5708					A	1831.9760	916.4916	1814.9494	907.9784	1813.9654	907.4863	17
4	369.1769	185.0921			351.1663	176.0868	E	1760.9389	880.9731	1743.9123	872.4598	1742.9283	871.9678	16
5	497.2718	249.1395	480.2453	240.6263	479.2613	240.1343	K	1631.8963	816.4518	1614.8697	807.9385	1613.8857	807.4465	15
6	625.3668	313.1870	608.3402	304.6738	607.3562	304.1817	K	1503.8013	752.4043	1486.7748	743.8910	1485.7908	743.3990	14
7	722.4196	361.7134	705.3930	353.2001	704.4090	352.7081	P	1375.7064	688.3568	1358.6798	679.8435	1357.6958	679.3515	13
8	793.4567	397.2320	776.4301	388.7187	775.4461	388.2267	A	1278.6536	639.8304	1261.6270	631.3172	1260.6430	630.8251	12
9	864.4938	432.7505	847.4672	424.2373	846.4832	423.7452	A	1207.6165	604.3119	1190.5899	595.7986	1189.6059	595.3066	11
10	1034.5993	517.8033	1017.5728	509.2900	1016.5887	508.7980	K	1136.5794	568.7933	1119.5528	560.2800	1118.5688	559.7880	10
11	1204.7048	602.8561	1187.6783	594.3428	1186.6943	593.8508	K	966.4738	483.7406	949.4473	475.2273	948.4633	474.7353	9
12	1305.7525	653.3799	1288.7260	644.8666	1287.7419	644.3746	T	796.3683	398.6878	779.3418	390.1745	778.3577	389.6825	8
13	1392.7845	696.8959	1375.7580	688.3826	1374.7740	687.8906	S	695.3206	348.1640	678.2941	339.6507	677.3101	339.1587	7
14	1493.8322	747.4197	1476.8057	738.9065	1475.8217	738.4145	T	608.2886	304.6479	591.2620	296.1347	590.2780	295.6427	6
15	1580.8642	790.9358	1563.8377	782.4225	1562.8537	781.9305	S	507.2409	254.1241	490.2144	245.6108	489.2304	245.1188	5
16	1681.9119	841.4596	1664.8854	832.9463	1663.9014	832.4543	T	420.2089	210.6081	403.1823	202.0948	402.1983	201.6028	4
17	1796.9389	898.9731	1779.9123	890.4598	1778.9283	889.9678	D	319.1612	160.0842	302.1347	151.5710	301.1506	151.0790	3

18	1853.9603	927.4838	1836.9338	918.9705	1835.9498	918.4785	G	204.1343	102.5708	187.1077	94.0575			2
19							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI BLAST search of [APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
77.1	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K10, K11 98.40%
58.2	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K6, K11 1.28%
48.0	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K5, K11 0.12%
48.0	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K6, K10 0.12%
44.2	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K5, K6 0.05%
40.1	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K5, K10 0.02%
25.5	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K10, K19 0.00%
19.8	1999.0585	-0.0000	APAEEKPAAKKTSTSTDGK	Acetyl K11, K19 0.00%
15.4	1999.0577	0.0008	SKIDVIDKEYMKRPK	
14.1	1999.0503	0.0082	KEPVKTPSPAPAAKISSR	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE **Mascot Search Results**

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KETYSSYIYK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 111539: 1308.66068 from(655.337580,2+) intensity(67607.4380) scans(4126) rawscans(sn4126) rtinseconds(1514.1556) index(202836)

Title: 3431: Scan 4126 (rt=25.2359) [D:\MSData\All\VELO23958.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1308.6601
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K1 : Dimethyl (K)
 Ions Score: 51 Expect: 0.00084
 Matches : 26/98 fragment ions using 42 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	157.1335	79.0704	140.1070	70.5571			K							10
2	286.1761	143.5917	269.1496	135.0784	268.1656	134.5864	E	1153.5412	577.2742	1136.5146	568.7610	1135.5306	568.2689	9
3	387.2238	194.1155	370.1973	185.6023	369.2132	185.1103	T	1024.4986	512.7529	1007.4720	504.2397	1006.4880	503.7477	8
4	550.2871	275.6472	533.2606	267.1339	532.2766	266.6419	Y	923.4509	462.2291	906.4244	453.7158	905.4403	453.2238	7
5	637.3192	319.1632	620.2926	310.6499	619.3086	310.1579	S	760.3876	380.6974	743.3610	372.1842	742.3770	371.6921	6
6	724.3512	362.6792	707.3246	354.1660	706.3406	353.6740	S	673.3556	337.1814	656.3290	328.6681	655.3450	328.1761	5
7	887.4145	444.2109	870.3880	435.6976	869.4040	435.2056	Y	586.3235	293.6654	569.2970	285.1521			4
8	1000.4986	500.7529	983.4720	492.2397	982.4880	491.7477	I	423.2602	212.1337	406.2336	203.6205			3
9	1163.5619	582.2846	1146.5354	573.7713	1145.5514	573.2793	Y	310.1761	155.5917	293.1496	147.0784			2
10							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KETYSSYIYK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
50.6	1308.6601	0.0005	KETYSSYIYK
21.8	1308.6591	0.0015	GDIHYIRLTK
16.9	1308.6607	-0.0001	TKRLISIYK
11.6	1308.6608	-0.0002	IPVIKHITTK
10.0	1308.6561	0.0045	KKENDDTIYK
10.0	1308.6561	0.0045	KKENDDTIYK
9.5	1308.6551	0.0055	KVSANDKNRK
9.1	1308.6608	-0.0002	QYMEKIREGR
9.1	1308.6607	-0.0001	TKRLISIYK
9.0	1308.6591	0.0015	KTQKFHNEK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KETYSSYIYKVLK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 174679: 1662.886392 from(555.302740,3+) intensity(41989.3130) scans(9021) rawscans(sn9021) rtinseconds(2997.0281) index(75479)

Title: 7476: Scan 9021 (rt=49.9505) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23668.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

109.09 to 1097.89

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1662.8868

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 46 Expect: 0.002

Matches : 27/128 fragment ions using 34 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							13
2	300.1554	150.5813	283.1288	142.0681	282.1448	141.5761	E	1493.7886	747.3980	1476.7621	738.8847	1475.7781	738.3927	12
3	401.2031	201.1052	384.1765	192.5919	383.1925	192.0999	T	1364.7460	682.8767	1347.7195	674.3634	1346.7355	673.8714	11
4	564.2664	282.6368	547.2399	274.1236	546.2558	273.6316	Y	1263.6984	632.3528	1246.6718	623.8395	1245.6878	623.3475	10
5	651.2984	326.1529	634.2719	317.6396	633.2879	317.1476	S	1100.6350	550.8211	1083.6085	542.3079	1082.6245	541.8159	9
6	738.3305	369.6689	721.3039	361.1556	720.3199	360.6636	S	1013.6030	507.3051	996.5764	498.7919	995.5924	498.2999	8
7	901.3938	451.2005	884.3672	442.6873	883.3832	442.1953	Y	926.5710	463.7891	909.5444	455.2758			7
8	1014.4779	507.7426	997.4513	499.2293	996.4673	498.7373	I	763.5076	382.2575	746.4811	373.7442			6
9	1177.5412	589.2742	1160.5146	580.7610	1159.5306	580.2689	Y	650.4236	325.7154	633.3970	317.2022			5
10	1305.6361	653.3217	1288.6096	644.8084	1287.6256	644.3164	K	487.3602	244.1838	470.3337	235.6705			4
11	1404.7046	702.8559	1387.6780	694.3426	1386.6940	693.8506	V	359.2653	180.1363	342.2387	171.6230			3
12	1517.7886	759.3980	1500.7621	750.8847	1499.7781	750.3927	L	260.1969	130.6021	243.1703	122.0888			2
13							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KETYSSYIYKVLK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
46.0	1662.8868	-0.0004	KETYSSYIYKVLK
16.4	1662.8842	0.0022	YNSNKREVAWGVAK
13.4	1662.8858	0.0006	AFNKVDNITLKHK
11.9	1662.8874	-0.0010	LGS AKLKSLILYR
11.4	1662.8858	0.0006	AFNKVDNITLKHK
11.3	1662.8858	0.0006	GLERSIINVLA WGK
11.2	1662.8858	0.0006	AFNKVDNITLKHK
11.2	1662.8858	0.0006	AFNKVDNITLKHK
10.8	1662.8842	0.0022	RPVLRNYFTADNK
7.1	1662.8842	0.0022	RPVLRNYFTADNK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KETYSSYIYK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 122225: 1360.594748 from(681.304650,2+) intensity(29592.3050) scans(4663) rawscans(sn4663) rtinseconds(1648.8972) index(306031)

Title: 3916: Scan 4663 (rt=27.4816) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23980.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

140.22 to 1333.48

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1360.5952

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

T3 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 45 Expect: 0.0012

Matches : 16/152 fragment ions using 20 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	129.1022	65.0548	112.0757	56.5415			K							10
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	E	1233.5075	617.2574	1216.4810	608.7441	1215.4969	608.2521	9
3	439.1588	220.0831	422.1323	211.5698	421.1483	211.0778	T	1104.4649	552.7361	1087.4384	544.2228	1086.4544	543.7308	8
4	602.2222	301.6147	585.1956	293.1014	584.2116	292.6094	Y	923.4509	462.2291	906.4244	453.7158	905.4403	453.2238	7
5	689.2542	345.1307	672.2277	336.6175	671.2436	336.1255	S	760.3876	380.6974	743.3610	372.1842	742.3770	371.6921	6
6	776.2862	388.6468	759.2597	380.1335	758.2757	379.6415	S	673.3556	337.1814	656.3290	328.6681	655.3450	328.1761	5
7	939.3496	470.1784	922.3230	461.6651	921.3390	461.1731	Y	586.3235	293.6654	569.2970	285.1521			4
8	1052.4336	526.7204	1035.4071	518.2072	1034.4231	517.7152	I	423.2602	212.1337	406.2336	203.6205			3
9	1215.4969	608.2521	1198.4704	599.7388	1197.4864	599.2468	Y	310.1761	155.5917	293.1496	147.0784			2
10							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KETYSSYIYK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
44.8	1360.5952	-0.0004	KETYSSYIYK	Phospho T3 98.87%
22.4	1360.5952	-0.0004	KETYSSYIYK	Phospho S6 0.56%
22.4	1360.5952	-0.0004	KETYSSYIYK	Phospho S5 0.56%
18.2	1360.5911	0.0036	KSDGNSILYK	
14.9	1360.5911	0.0036	NTDKEKAEYK	
14.7	1360.5911	0.0036	KSDGNSILYK	
9.8	1360.5911	0.0036	NTDKEKAEYK	
7.5	1360.6007	-0.0060	SSHPQNGSEYK	
6.4	1360.5885	0.0063	VSGGRSNHNDPK	
5.3	1360.6013	-0.0066	KRTNRNNTK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KETYSSYIYK**

Found in **H2B1_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02293|H2B1_YEAST Histone H2B.1 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 122217: 1360.589448 from(681.302000,2+) intensity(12669.4620) scans(3860) rawscans(sn3860) rtinseconds(1438.0211) index(320459)

Title: 3176: Scan 3860 (rt=23.967) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23982.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1360.5952

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

S6 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 28 Expect: 0.065 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ⁺⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ⁺⁺⁺	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	129.1022	65.0548	112.0757	56.5415			K							10
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	E	1233.5075	617.2574	1216.4810	608.7441	1215.4969	608.2521	9
3	359.1925	180.0999	342.1660	171.5866	341.1819	171.0946	T	1104.4649	552.7361	1087.4384	544.2228	1086.4544	543.7308	8
4	522.2558	261.6316	505.2293	253.1183	504.2453	252.6263	Y	1003.4172	502.2123	986.3907	493.6990	985.4067	493.2070	7
5	609.2879	305.1476	592.2613	296.6343	591.2773	296.1423	S	840.3539	420.6806	823.3274	412.1673	822.3433	411.6753	6
6	776.2862	388.6468	759.2597	380.1335	758.2757	379.6415	S	753.3219	377.1646	736.2953	368.6513	735.3113	368.1593	5
7	939.3496	470.1784	922.3230	461.6651	921.3390	461.1731	Y	586.3235	293.6654	569.2970	285.1521			4
8	1052.4336	526.7204	1035.4071	518.2072	1034.4231	517.7152	I	423.2602	212.1337	406.2336	203.6205			3
9	1215.4969	608.2521	1198.4704	599.7388	1197.4864	599.2468	Y	310.1761	155.5917	293.1496	147.0784			2
10							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KETYSSYIYK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
27.7	1360.5952	-0.0057	KETYSSYIYK
27.7	1360.5952	-0.0057	KETYSSYIYK
27.7	1360.5952	-0.0057	KETYSSYIYK
18.2	1360.5911	-0.0017	KSDGNSILYK
11.6	1360.5911	-0.0017	KSDGNSILYK
7.9	1360.5925	-0.0030	SAANKHNWPK
5.6	1360.5869	0.0025	VSFKPGSFYK
1.3	1360.5869	0.0025	VSFKPGSFYK
0.5	1360.5911	-0.0017	YEAKEKDTNK
0.2	1360.5958	-0.0063	KLFSTRGTK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **ETYSSYIYK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 86023: 1194.545708 from(598.280130,2+) intensity(28208.6840) scans(4996) rawscans(sn4996)

rtinseconds(1663.85) index(290344)

Title: 4236: Scan 4996 (rt=27.7308) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23978.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen. Search range: 74.15 to 1089.42

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1194.5444

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K9 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 35 **Expect:** 0.0022

Matches : 16/72 fragment ions using 31 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{***}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286	112.0393	56.5233	E							9
2	231.0975	116.0524	213.0870	107.0471	T	1066.5092	533.7582	1049.4826	525.2449	1048.4986	524.7529	8
3	394.1609	197.5841	376.1503	188.5788	Y	965.4615	483.2344	948.4349	474.7211	947.4509	474.2291	7
4	481.1929	241.1001	463.1823	232.0948	S	802.3981	401.7027	785.3716	393.1894	784.3876	392.6974	6
5	568.2249	284.6161	550.2144	275.6108	S	715.3661	358.1867	698.3396	349.6734	697.3556	349.1814	5
6	731.2883	366.1478	713.2777	357.1425	Y	628.3341	314.6707	611.3075	306.1574			4
7	844.3723	422.6898	826.3618	413.6845	I	465.2708	233.1390	448.2442	224.6257			3
8	1007.4357	504.2215	989.4251	495.2162	Y	352.1867	176.5970	335.1601	168.0837			2
9					K	189.1234	95.0653	172.0968	86.5520			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [ETYSSYIYK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
34.9	1194.5444	0.0013	ETYSSYIYK
6.1	1194.5451	0.0006	SSLIFVTIR
6.0	1194.5451	0.0006	SSLIFVTIR
6.0	1194.5451	0.0006	RYLTSIVK
4.1	1194.5517	-0.0060	IFDSSQTNNK
2.6	1194.5451	0.0006	FPKSGKSSK
1.4	1194.5517	-0.0060	KGDEYNGNDK
1.3	1194.5517	-0.0060	TLTQYDGNNK
0.9	1194.5484	-0.0027	KTSKSVKGM
0.1	1194.5451	0.0006	LQSGSKFVK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **ETYSSYIYK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 80912: 1166.549668 from(584.282110,2+) intensity(19309.8980) scans(5325) rawscans(sn5325)

rtinseconds(1741.7943) index(290635)

Title: 4527: Scan 5325 (rt=29.0299) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23978.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

84.04

to

1122.67

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1166.5495

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K9 : Methyl (K)

Ions Score: 27 **Expect:** 0.0067

Matches : 9/72 fragment ions using 18 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286	112.0393	56.5233	E							9
2	231.0975	116.0524	213.0870	107.0471	T	1038.5142	519.7608	1021.4877	511.2475	1020.5037	510.7555	8
3	394.1609	197.5841	376.1503	188.5788	Y	937.4666	469.2369	920.4400	460.7236	919.4560	460.2316	7
4	481.1929	241.1001	463.1823	232.0948	S	774.4032	387.7053	757.3767	379.1920	756.3927	378.7000	6
5	568.2249	284.6161	550.2144	275.6108	S	687.3712	344.1892	670.3447	335.6760	669.3606	335.1840	5
6	731.2883	366.1478	713.2777	357.1425	Y	600.3392	300.6732	583.3126	292.1600			4
7	844.3723	422.6898	826.3618	413.6845	I	437.2758	219.1416	420.2493	210.6283			3
8	1007.4357	504.2215	989.4251	495.2162	Y	324.1918	162.5995	307.1652	154.0863			2
9					K	161.1285	81.0679	144.1019	72.5546			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [ETYSSYIYK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
27.0	1166.5495	0.0001	ETYSSYIYK
3.6	1166.5501	-0.0005	SKKKAFTK
3.5	1166.5485	0.0012	DEIHKFTR
1.7	1166.5455	0.0042	ENVKSSYEK
1.6	1166.5525	-0.0029	FSFLRSFK
1.4	1166.5489	0.0008	TLSCISETSK
1.1	1166.5455	0.0042	EEEEKEYR
0.9	1166.5445	0.0052	TLKAONGASR
0.5	1166.5444	0.0052	SRAEREQK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **VLKQTHPTGISQK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 162951: 1592.851062 from(531.957630,3+) intensity(30684.2190) scans(2149) rawscans(sn2149) rtinseconds(1015.2969) index(55618)

Title: 1713: Scan 2149 (rt=16.9216) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23666.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

81.12 to 945.5

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1592.8522
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K3 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 33 Expect: 0.094
 Matches : 13/140 fragment ions using 13 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	100.0757	50.5415					V							14
2	213.1598	107.0835					L	1494.7911	747.8992	1477.7645	739.3859	1476.7805	738.8939	13
3	383.2653	192.1363	366.2387	183.6230			K	1381.7070	691.3571	1364.6805	682.8439	1363.6965	682.3519	12
4	511.3239	256.1656	494.2973	247.6523			Q	1211.6015	606.3044	1194.5749	597.7911	1193.5909	597.2991	11
5	612.3715	306.6894	595.3450	298.1761	594.3610	297.6841	T	1083.5429	542.2751	1066.5164	533.7618	1065.5323	533.2698	10
6	749.4305	375.2189	732.4039	366.7056	731.4199	366.2136	H	982.4952	491.7513	965.4687	483.2380	964.4847	482.7460	9
7	846.4832	423.7452	829.4567	415.2320	828.4726	414.7400	P	845.4363	423.2218	828.4098	414.7085	827.4258	414.2165	8
8	961.5102	481.2587	944.4836	472.7454	943.4996	472.2534	D	748.3836	374.6954	731.3570	366.1821	730.3730	365.6901	7
9	1062.5578	531.7826	1045.5313	523.2693	1044.5473	522.7773	T	633.3566	317.1819	616.3301	308.6687	615.3461	308.1767	6
10	1119.5793	560.2933	1102.5528	551.7800	1101.5687	551.2880	G	532.3089	266.6581	515.2824	258.1448	514.2984	257.6528	5
11	1232.6634	616.8353	1215.6368	608.3220	1214.6528	607.8300	I	475.2875	238.1474	458.2609	229.6341	457.2769	229.1421	4
12	1319.6954	660.3513	1302.6688	651.8381	1301.6848	651.3461	S	362.2034	181.6053	345.1769	173.0921	344.1928	172.6001	3
13	1447.7540	724.3806	1430.7274	715.8673	1429.7434	715.3753	Q	275.1714	138.0893	258.1448	129.5761			2
14							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [VLKQTHPDTGISQK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
32.8	1592.8522	-0.0012	VLKQTHPDTGISQK
20.8	1592.8514	-0.0003	MVVFKNIGHIITK
17.8	1592.8569	-0.0058	VLAHEAQNRMNLR
14.3	1592.8569	-0.0058	VLAHEAQNRMNLR
13.6	1592.8511	-0.0001	NKSVRSRNNANK
13.6	1592.8511	-0.0001	NKSVRSRNNANK
13.5	1592.8539	-0.0028	IVKSLETGIDQVR
13.5	1592.8539	-0.0028	LGTGLGKSAIDGVKK
13.5	1592.8539	-0.0028	LGTGLGKSAIDGVKK
13.5	1592.8539	-0.0028	LGTGLGKSAIDGVKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

 Mascot Search Results**Peptide View**MS/MS Fragmentation of **IATEASKLAAYNK**Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2Match to Query 134482: 1420.754688 from(711.384620,2+) intensity(31025.3330) scans(4830-4839) rawscans(sn4830:sn4839)
rtinseconds(1748.5231-1751.0392) index(159720)

Title: 3952: Sum of 2 scans in range 4830 (rt=29.1421) to 4839 (rt=29.184) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23670.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1420.7561

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K7 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 24 Expect: 0.058

Matches : 19/114 fragment ions using 53 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493					I							13
2	185.1285	93.0679					A	1308.6794	654.8433	1291.6529	646.3301	1290.6688	645.8381	12
3	286.1761	143.5917			268.1656	134.5864	T	1237.6423	619.3248	1220.6157	610.8115	1219.6317	610.3195	11
4	415.2187	208.1130			397.2082	199.1077	E	1136.5946	568.8009	1119.5681	560.2877	1118.5841	559.7957	10
5	486.2558	243.6316			468.2453	234.6263	A	1007.5520	504.2796	990.5255	495.7664	989.5415	495.2744	9
6	573.2879	287.1476			555.2773	278.1423	S	936.5149	468.7611	919.4884	460.2478	918.5043	459.7558	8
7	743.3934	372.2003	726.3668	363.6871	725.3828	363.1951	K	849.4829	425.2451	832.4563	416.7318			7
8	856.4775	428.7424	839.4509	420.2291	838.4669	419.7371	L	679.3774	340.1923	662.3508	331.6790			6
9	927.5146	464.2609	910.4880	455.7477	909.5040	455.2556	A	566.2933	283.6503	549.2667	275.1370			5
10	998.5517	499.7795	981.5251	491.2662	980.5411	490.7742	A	495.2562	248.1317	478.2296	239.6185			4
11	1161.6150	581.3111	1144.5885	572.7979	1143.6045	572.3059	Y	424.2191	212.6132	407.1925	204.0999			3
12	1275.6579	638.3326	1258.6314	629.8193	1257.6474	629.3273	N	261.1557	131.0815	244.1292	122.5682			2
13							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [IATEASKLAAYNK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
23.6	1420.7561	-0.0014	IATEASKLAAYNK
9.9	1420.7496	0.0051	FLSKKGIISAK
9.1	1420.7479	0.0068	LLSFGAGPNPLKK
7.8	1420.7479	0.0068	TSYKRKYTPK
7.8	1420.7479	0.0068	TSYKRKYTPK
7.5	1420.7570	-0.0023	DMKNIFCIKPK
7.4	1420.7479	0.0068	YKAGKYLKTNK
7.1	1420.7562	-0.0015	LFKSSDGVNEKK
6.0	1420.7479	0.0068	NTKLYKGAKYK
5.7	1420.7575	-0.0028	ERNNSLVWPHK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **LILPGELAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 37555: 952.595368 from(477.304960,2+) intensity(15880.6040) scans(14418) rawscans(sn14418) rtinseconds(4933.5697) index(269171)

Title: 11652: Scan 14418 (rt=82.2262) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23664.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home, Left Arrow, Magnifying Glass (Zoom In), Magnifying Glass (Zoom Out), Magnifying Glass (Reset), Input field: 83.96 to 940.61, Magnifying Glass (Search), Right Arrow

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 952.5957

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Ions Score: 38 Expect: 0.0041 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493			L							9
2	227.1754	114.0913			I	840.5189	420.7631	823.4924	412.2498	822.5084	411.7578	8
3	340.2595	170.6334			L	727.4349	364.2211	710.4083	355.7078	709.4243	355.2158	7
4	437.3122	219.1598			P	614.3508	307.6790	597.3243	299.1658	596.3402	298.6738	6
5	494.3337	247.6705			G	517.2980	259.1527	500.2715	250.6394	499.2875	250.1474	5
6	623.3763	312.1918	605.3657	303.1865	E	460.2766	230.6419	443.2500	222.1287	442.2660	221.6366	4
7	736.4604	368.7338	718.4498	359.7285	L	331.2340	166.1206	314.2074	157.6074			3
8	807.4975	404.2524	789.4869	395.2471	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653			2
9					K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [LILPGELAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
38.2	952.5957	-0.0003	LILPGELAK
22.5	952.5957	-0.0003	ILINDPIK
22.5	952.5957	-0.0003	EPLPSLKK
22.5	952.5957	-0.0003	EPLPSLKK
22.5	952.5957	-0.0003	EPLPSLKK
22.5	952.5957	-0.0003	EPLPSLKK
13.1	952.5957	-0.0003	ILPLDLQK
7.5	952.5957	-0.0003	IPETPVKK
7.5	952.5957	-0.0003	IPETPVKK
7.0	952.5957	-0.0003	IIGIPKDK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **LILPGELAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 48552: 994.605748 from(498.310150,2+) intensity(389924.0900) scans(7593) rawscans(sn7593) rtinseconds(2563.5222) index(74306)

Title: 6303: Scan 7593 (rt=42.7254) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23668.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 994.6062

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K9 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 15 Expect: 0.28 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493			L							9
2	227.1754	114.0913			I	882.5295	441.7684	865.5029	433.2551	864.5189	432.7631	8
3	340.2595	170.6334			L	769.4454	385.2264	752.4189	376.7131	751.4349	376.2211	7
4	437.3122	219.1598			P	656.3614	328.6843	639.3348	320.1710	638.3508	319.6790	6
5	494.3337	247.6705			G	559.3086	280.1579	542.2821	271.6447	541.2980	271.1527	5
6	623.3763	312.1918	605.3657	303.1865	E	502.2871	251.6472	485.2606	243.1339	484.2766	242.6419	4
7	736.4604	368.7338	718.4498	359.7285	L	373.2445	187.1259	356.2180	178.6126			3
8	807.4975	404.2524	789.4869	395.2471	A	260.1605	130.5839	243.1339	122.0706			2
9					K	189.1234	95.0653	172.0968	86.5520			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [LILPGELAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
15.2	994.6062	-0.0005	EPLPSLKK
15.2	994.6062	-0.0005	EPLPSLKK
15.2	994.6062	-0.0005	LILPGELAK
8.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKGSKK
8.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKGSKK
3.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKKGTK
3.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKKGTK
3.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKKGTK
3.7	994.6052	0.0005	RKKKGTK
3.5	994.6036	0.0022	GIITRSHR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **LILPGELAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 41957: 966.611588 from(484.313070,2+) intensity(25441.6130) scans(8548) rawscans(sn8548) rtinseconds(2549.5655) index(293444)

Title: 7336: Scan 8548 (rt=42.4928) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23978.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

99.11

to 841.41

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 966.6113

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K9 : Methyl (K)

Ions Score: 20 Expect: 0.026 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493			L							9
2	227.1754	114.0913			I	854.5346	427.7709	837.5080	419.2577	836.5240	418.7656	8
3	340.2595	170.6334			L	741.4505	371.2289	724.4240	362.7156	723.4400	362.2236	7
4	437.3122	219.1598			P	628.3665	314.6869	611.3399	306.1736	610.3559	305.6816	6
5	494.3337	247.6705			G	531.3137	266.1605	514.2871	257.6472	513.3031	257.1552	5
6	623.3763	312.1918	605.3657	303.1865	E	474.2922	237.6498	457.2657	229.1365	456.2817	228.6445	4
7	736.4604	368.7338	718.4498	359.7285	L	345.2496	173.1285	328.2231	164.6152			3
8	807.4975	404.2524	789.4869	395.2471	A	232.1656	116.5864	215.1390	108.0731			2
9					K	161.1285	81.0679	144.1019	72.5546			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [LILPGELAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
20.3	966.6113	0.0002	LILPGELAK
19.1	966.6113	0.0003	EPLPSLKK
19.1	966.6113	0.0002	EPLPSLKK
19.1	966.6113	0.0002	EPLPSLKK
19.1	966.6113	0.0002	ILINDPIK
19.1	966.6113	0.0002	LIITPIQK
3.3	966.6113	0.0003	PIEHLNK
2.6	966.6113	0.0002	IIGIPKDK
2.6	966.6113	0.0002	IIGIPKDK
1.9	966.6087	0.0029	GGKRGRPK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **LILPGELAK**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 45234: 980.627228 from(491.320890,2+) intensity(24935.5640) scans(10840) rawscans(sn10840)

rtinseconds(2825.3616) index(341195)

Title: 9529: Scan 10840 (rt=47.0894) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23984.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen 75.21 to 968.6

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 980.6270

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K9 : Dimethyl (K)

Ions Score: 26 **Expect:** 0.066 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493			L							9
2	227.1754	114.0913			I	868.5502	434.7788	851.5237	426.2655	850.5397	425.7735	8
3	340.2595	170.6334			L	755.4662	378.2367	738.4396	369.7234	737.4556	369.2314	7
4	437.3122	219.1598			P	642.3821	321.6947	625.3556	313.1814	624.3715	312.6894	6
5	494.3337	247.6705			G	545.3293	273.1683	528.3028	264.6550	527.3188	264.1630	5
6	623.3763	312.1918	605.3657	303.1865	E	488.3079	244.6576	471.2813	236.1443	470.2973	235.6523	4
7	736.4604	368.7338	718.4498	359.7285	L	359.2653	180.1363	342.2387	171.6230			3
8	807.4975	404.2524	789.4869	395.2471	A	246.1812	123.5942	229.1547	115.0810			2
9					K	175.1441	88.0757	158.1176	79.5624			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [LILPGELAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
26.5	980.6270	0.0002	LILPGELAK
14.4	980.6270	0.0002	EPLPSLKK
14.4	980.6270	0.0002	EPLPSLKK
7.9	980.6270	0.0002	LLNELPLK
3.7	980.6270	0.0002	LLTPLPSK
1.2	980.6243	0.0029	RGKQPKR
0.9	980.6270	0.0002	PIEHLNK
0.7	980.6270	0.0002	ILPLDLQK
0.2	980.6270	0.0002	IPETPVKK
0.2	980.6270	0.0002	IPETPVKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 241325: 2058.935562 from(687.319130,3+) intensity(36024.4840) scans(1976) rawscans(sn1976) rtinseconds(948.7934) index(157340)

Title: 1572: Scan 1976 (rt=15.8132) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23670.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 2058.9371

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

T17 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 25 Expect: 0.036

Matches : 51/298 fragment ions using 73 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	138.0662	69.5367					H							19
2	209.1033	105.0553					A	1922.8855	961.9464	1905.8590	953.4331	1904.8750	952.9411	18
3	308.1717	154.5895					V	1851.8484	926.4278	1834.8219	917.9146	1833.8379	917.4226	17
4	395.2037	198.1055			377.1932	189.1002	S	1752.7800	876.8936	1735.7535	868.3804	1734.7694	867.8884	16
5	524.2463	262.6268			506.2358	253.6215	E	1665.7480	833.3776	1648.7214	824.8644	1647.7374	824.3723	15
6	581.2678	291.1375			563.2572	282.1323	G	1536.7054	768.8563	1519.6788	760.3431	1518.6948	759.8510	14
7	682.3155	341.6614			664.3049	332.6561	T	1479.6839	740.3456	1462.6574	731.8323	1461.6734	731.3403	13
8	838.4166	419.7119	821.3900	411.1987	820.4060	410.7067	R	1378.6362	689.8218	1361.6097	681.3085	1360.6257	680.8165	12
9	909.4537	455.2305	892.4272	446.7172	891.4431	446.2252	A	1222.5351	611.7712	1205.5086	603.2579	1204.5246	602.7659	11
10	1008.5221	504.7647	991.4956	496.2514	990.5116	495.7594	V	1151.4980	576.2526	1134.4715	567.7394	1133.4874	567.2474	10
11	1109.5698	555.2885	1092.5432	546.7753	1091.5592	546.2833	T	1052.4296	526.7184	1035.4030	518.2052	1034.4190	517.7132	9
12	1237.6648	619.3360	1220.6382	610.8227	1219.6542	610.3307	K	951.3819	476.1946	934.3554	467.6813	933.3714	467.1893	8
13	1400.7281	700.8677	1383.7015	692.3544	1382.7175	691.8624	Y	823.2870	412.1471	806.2604	403.6338	805.2764	403.1418	7
14	1487.7601	744.3837	1470.7336	735.8704	1469.7496	735.3784	S	660.2236	330.6155	643.1971	322.1022	642.2131	321.6102	6
15	1574.7921	787.8997	1557.7656	779.3864	1556.7816	778.8944	S	573.1916	287.0994	556.1651	278.5862	555.1810	278.0942	5
16	1661.8242	831.4157	1644.7976	822.9025	1643.8136	822.4104	S	486.1596	243.5834	469.1330	235.0701	468.1490	234.5781	4
17	1842.8382	921.9227	1825.8116	913.4095	1824.8276	912.9174	T	399.1275	200.0674	382.1010	191.5541	381.1170	191.0621	3
18	1970.8968	985.9520	1953.8702	977.4387	1952.8862	976.9467	Q	218.1135	109.5604	201.0870	101.0471			2

19						A	90.0550	45.5311							1
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NCBI BLAST search of [HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
24.7	2058.9371	-0.0016	HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho T17 51.24%
22.3	2058.9371	-0.0016	HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S15 29.35%
19.6	2058.9371	-0.0016	HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S16 15.73%
9.7	2058.9371	-0.0016	HAVSEGTRAVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S14 1.64%
8.8	2058.9346	0.0010	STRFIPKPLYGSNOK	
8.3	2058.9388	-0.0032	PQDASSSSLSSPPKIRK	
8.3	2058.9388	-0.0032	PQDASSSSLSSPPKIRK	
6.9	2058.9388	-0.0032	KGKSKHSSDEGDKSK	
6.9	2058.9388	-0.0032	KGKSKHSSDEGDKSK	
6.9	2058.9388	-0.0032	KGKSKHSSDEGDKSK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **AVTKYSSSTQA**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 84530: 1183.571928 from(592.793240,2+) intensity(45193.7070) scans(2700) rawscans(sn2700) rtinseconds(1120.6672) index(188209)

Title: 2246: Scan 2700 (rt=18.6778) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23956.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1183.5721

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K4 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 57 Expect: 1.1e-05

Matches : 23/104 fragment ions using 25 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							11
2	171.1128	86.0600					V	1113.5422	557.2748	1096.5157	548.7615	1095.5317	548.2695	10
3	272.1605	136.5839			254.1499	127.5786	T	1014.4738	507.7406	997.4473	499.2273	996.4633	498.7353	9
4	442.2660	221.6366	425.2395	213.1234	424.2554	212.6314	K	913.4262	457.2167	896.3996	448.7034	895.4156	448.2114	8
5	605.3293	303.1683	588.3028	294.6550	587.3188	294.1630	Y	743.3206	372.1640	726.2941	363.6507	725.3101	363.1587	7
6	692.3614	346.6843	675.3348	338.1710	674.3508	337.6790	S	580.2573	290.6323	563.2307	282.1190	562.2467	281.6270	6
7	779.3934	390.2003	762.3668	381.6871	761.3828	381.1951	S	493.2253	247.1163	476.1987	238.6030	475.2147	238.1110	5
8	866.4254	433.7163	849.3989	425.2031	848.4149	424.7111	S	406.1932	203.6003	389.1667	195.0870	388.1827	194.5950	4
9	967.4731	484.2402	950.4466	475.7269	949.4625	475.2349	T	319.1612	160.0842	302.1347	151.5710	301.1506	151.0790	3
10	1095.5317	548.2695	1078.5051	539.7562	1077.5211	539.2642	Q	218.1135	109.5604	201.0870	101.0471			2
11							A	90.0550	45.5311					1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [AVTKYSSSTQA](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
56.8	1183.5721	-0.0001	AVTKYSSSTQA
3.6	1183.5751	-0.0031	KTFEPTR
1.9	1183.5750	-0.0031	KTFEPTR
1.7	1183.5710	0.0009	RSSRTNGDK
0.9	1183.5750	-0.0031	KTFEPTR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **AVTKYSSSTQA**

Found in **H2B2_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02294|H2B2_YEAST Histone H2B.2 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HTB2 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 90998: 1221.527328 from(611.770940,2+) intensity(63813.9770) scans(1817) rawscans(sn1817) rtinseconds(907.3459) index(258984)

Title: 1465: Scan 1817 (rt=15.1224) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS23664.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\530 Final H2A H2B yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), zoom in, zoom out, pan, and search. Search range: 100.26 to 1152.38.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1221.5278

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

S6 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 28 Expect: 0.0046

Matches : 21/164 fragment ions using 33 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	72.0444	36.5258					A							11
2	171.1128	86.0600					V	1151.4980	576.2526	1134.4715	567.7394	1133.4874	567.2474	10
3	272.1605	136.5839			254.1499	127.5786	T	1052.4296	526.7184	1035.4030	518.2052	1034.4190	517.7132	9
4	400.2554	200.6314	383.2289	192.1181	382.2449	191.6261	K	951.3819	476.1946	934.3554	467.6813	933.3714	467.1893	8
5	563.3188	282.1630	546.2922	273.6498	545.3082	273.1577	Y	823.2870	412.1471	806.2604	403.6338	805.2764	403.1418	7
6	730.3171	365.6622	713.2906	357.1489	712.3066	356.6569	S	660.2236	330.6155	643.1971	322.1022	642.2131	321.6102	6
7	817.3492	409.1782	800.3226	400.6649	799.3386	400.1729	S	493.2253	247.1163	476.1987	238.6030	475.2147	238.1110	5
8	904.3812	452.6942	887.3546	444.1810	886.3706	443.6890	S	406.1932	203.6003	389.1667	195.0870	388.1827	194.5950	4
9	1005.4289	503.2181	988.4023	494.7048	987.4183	494.2128	T	319.1612	160.0842	302.1347	151.5710	301.1506	151.0790	3
10	1133.4874	567.2474	1116.4609	558.7341	1115.4769	558.2421	Q	218.1135	109.5604	201.0870	101.0471			2
11							A	90.0550	45.5311					1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [AVTKYSSSTQA](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
28.1	1221.5278	-0.0005	AVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S6 73.83%
22.5	1221.5278	-0.0005	AVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S7 20.38%
15.3	1221.5278	-0.0005	AVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho S8 3.88%
10.1	1221.5278	-0.0005	AVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho T9 1.16%
8.2	1221.5278	-0.0005	AVTKYSSSTQA	Phospho T3 0.75%
3.0	1221.5229	0.0044	LSKINSQMK	
1.2	1221.5319	-0.0045	DGELFYGLSK	
1.1	1221.5251	0.0022	GRSNDHAHTR	
1.0	1221.5325	-0.0052	KROHSSCK	
1.0	1221.5325	-0.0052	KROHSSCK	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KSTGGKAPR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 15297: 984.534408 from(493.274480,2+) intensity(15473.0830) scans(914) rawscans(sn914) rtinseconds(633.2113) index(110881)

Title: 669: Scan 914 (rt=10.5535) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25245.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, zoom reset, search range: 75.14 to 926.38, zoom in, right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 984.5352

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

K6 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 63 **Expect:** 1.7e-05

Matches: 22/82 fragment ions using 37 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							9
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	S	815.4370	408.2221	798.4104	399.7089	797.4264	399.2169	8
3	359.1925	180.0999	342.1660	171.5866	341.1819	171.0946	T	728.4050	364.7061	711.3784	356.1928	710.3944	355.7008	7
4	416.2140	208.6106	399.1874	200.0974	398.2034	199.6053	G	627.3573	314.1823	610.3307	305.6690			6
5	473.2354	237.1214	456.2089	228.6081	455.2249	228.1161	G	570.3358	285.6715	553.3093	277.1583			5
6	643.3410	322.1741	626.3144	313.6608	625.3304	313.1688	K	513.3144	257.1608	496.2878	248.6475			4
7	714.3781	357.6927	697.3515	349.1794	696.3675	348.6874	A	343.2088	172.1081	326.1823	163.5948			3
8	811.4308	406.2191	794.4043	397.7058	793.4203	397.2138	P	272.1717	136.5895	255.1452	128.0762			2
9							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KSTGGKAPR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
63.2	984.5352	-0.0008	KSTGGKAPR
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	RSTTSKK
33.4	984.5369	-0.0025	RSTTSKK
22.3	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTKSGKK
22.3	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK
22.3	984.5369	-0.0025	KSTTSRK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KSAPSTGGVK**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 21007: 1052.489568 from(527.252060,2+) intensity(14674.1880) scans(1718) rawscans(sn1718) rtinseconds(887.8376) index(87783)

Title: 1329: Scan 1718 (rt=14.7973) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25241.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen. Search range: 93.97 to 983.48

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1052.4903

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

S2 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 23 Expect: 0.14

Matches : 20/152 fragment ions using 40 most intense peaks (help)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							10
2	338.1112	169.5592	321.0846	161.0459	320.1006	160.5539	S	883.3921	442.1997	866.3655	433.6864	865.3815	433.1944	9
3	409.1483	205.0778	392.1217	196.5645	391.1377	196.0725	A	716.3937	358.7005	699.3672	350.1872	698.3832	349.6952	8
4	506.2010	253.6042	489.1745	245.0909	488.1905	244.5989	P	645.3566	323.1819	628.3301	314.6687	627.3461	314.1767	7
5	593.2331	297.1202	576.2065	288.6069	575.2225	288.1149	S	548.3039	274.6556	531.2773	266.1423	530.2933	265.6503	6
6	694.2807	347.6440	677.2542	339.1307	676.2702	338.6387	T	461.2718	231.1396	444.2453	222.6263	443.2613	222.1343	5
7	751.3022	376.1547	734.2757	367.6415	733.2916	367.1495	G	360.2241	180.6157	343.1976	172.1024			4
8	808.3237	404.6655	791.2971	396.1522	790.3131	395.6602	G	303.2027	152.1050	286.1761	143.5917			3
9	907.3921	454.1997	890.3655	445.6864	889.3815	445.1944	V	246.1812	123.5942	229.1547	115.0810			2
10							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KSAPSTGGVK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
22.8	1052.4903	-0.0008	KSAPSTGGVK
12.8	1052.4943	-0.0048	KTAYSSFK
11.3	1052.4903	-0.0008	LNTPSVNK
8.8	1052.4903	-0.0007	KSEEKLR
8.8	1052.4903	-0.0007	KSGDVELR
8.6	1052.4903	-0.0007	KSKGENVK
7.7	1052.4903	-0.0007	KSVANKDK
6.6	1052.4903	-0.0008	LNTPSVNK
4.9	1052.4903	-0.0007	QQALEAVSK
4.9	1052.4903	-0.0007	AVSRIEEK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KQLASKAAR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 21307: 1055.607988 from(528.811270,2+) intensity(175468.8800) scans(2294) rawscans(sn2294)
rtinseconds(985.9898) index(32175)

Title: 1869: Scan 2294 (rt=16.4332) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25233.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

75.26

to

986.62

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1055.6087

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

K6 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 85 **Expect:** 2.1e-07

Matches: 17/80 fragment ions using 20 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							9
2	299.1714	150.0893	282.1448	141.5761			Q	886.5105	443.7589	869.4839	435.2456	868.4999	434.7536	8
3	412.2554	206.6314	395.2289	198.1181			L	758.4519	379.7296	741.4254	371.2163	740.4413	370.7243	7
4	483.2926	242.1499	466.2660	233.6366			A	645.3679	323.1876	628.3413	314.6743	627.3573	314.1823	6
5	570.3246	285.6659	553.2980	277.1527	552.3140	276.6606	S	574.3307	287.6690	557.3042	279.1557	556.3202	278.6637	5
6	740.4301	370.7187	723.4036	362.2054	722.4196	361.7134	K	487.2987	244.1530	470.2722	235.6397			4
7	811.4672	406.2373	794.4407	397.7240	793.4567	397.2320	A	317.1932	159.1002	300.1666	150.5870			3
8	882.5043	441.7558	865.4778	433.2425	864.4938	432.7505	A	246.1561	123.5817	229.1295	115.0684			2
9							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KQLASKAAR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
85.3	1055.6087	-0.0007	KQLASKAAR
27.1	1055.6087	-0.0007	AKGLAARGDK
23.9	1055.6087	-0.0007	AVOERNLAK
22.6	1055.6087	-0.0007	QKEKAKAR
22.4	1055.6087	-0.0007	KQEKAAGR
20.5	1055.6087	-0.0007	KQEKAAGR
19.9	1055.6087	-0.0007	KRAAQEKK
19.9	1055.6087	-0.0007	KRAAQEKK
18.9	1055.6087	-0.0007	AKGLAARGDK
18.9	1055.6087	-0.0007	AKGLAARGDK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KSAPSTGGVK**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 14742: 972.523888 from(487.269220,2+) intensity(12132.8630) scans(1363) rawscans(sn1363) rtinseconds(720.2363) index(46363)

Title: 1051: Scan 1363 (rt=12.0039) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25235.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen Search Range: 112.22 to 927.43

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 972.5240

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 40 Expect: 0.0074

Matches : 12/98 fragment ions using 19 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							10
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	S	803.4258	402.2165	786.3992	393.7032	785.4152	393.2112	9
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	A	716.3937	358.7005	699.3672	350.1872	698.3832	349.6952	8
4	426.2347	213.6210	409.2082	205.1077	408.2241	204.6157	P	645.3566	323.1819	628.3301	314.6687	627.3461	314.1767	7
5	513.2667	257.1370	496.2402	248.6237	495.2562	248.1317	S	548.3039	274.6556	531.2773	266.1423	530.2933	265.6503	6
6	614.3144	307.6608	597.2879	299.1476	596.3039	298.6556	T	461.2718	231.1396	444.2453	222.6263	443.2613	222.1343	5
7	671.3359	336.1716	654.3093	327.6583	653.3253	327.1663	G	360.2241	180.6157	343.1976	172.1024			4
8	728.3573	364.6823	711.3308	356.1690	710.3468	355.6770	G	303.2027	152.1050	286.1761	143.5917			3
9	827.4258	414.2165	810.3992	405.7032	809.4152	405.2112	V	246.1812	123.5942	229.1547	115.0810			2
10							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI BLAST search of [KSAPSTGGVK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
39.6	972.5240	-0.0001	KSAPSTGGVK
15.9	972.5280	-0.0041	KTAYSSFK
14.0	972.5240	-0.0001	KSKGENVK
10.2	972.5240	-0.0001	VTGNEKSPK
10.2	972.5240	-0.0001	KSKEAQAK
9.3	972.5240	-0.0001	KSKEAQAK
8.5	972.5240	-0.0001	VDNKKASK
8.5	972.5240	-0.0001	VDNKKASK
8.4	972.5240	-0.0001	KSDKGGKK
8.2	972.5240	-0.0001	KSVANKDK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KSAPSTGGVKKPHR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c)
GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 60884: 1532.842362 from(511.954730,3+) intensity(8879.4229) scans(1235) rawscans(sn1235) rtinseconds(734.2615)
index(937)

Title: 938: Scan 1235 (rt=12.2377) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25229.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

66.04 to 1097.63

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1532.8423

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

K10 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 22 Expect: 0.11

Matches : 13/138 fragment ions using 15 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ⁺⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ⁺⁺⁺	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							14
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	S	1363.7441	682.3757	1346.7175	673.8624	1345.7335	673.3704	13
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	A	1276.7120	638.8597	1259.6855	630.3464	1258.7015	629.8544	12
4	426.2347	213.6210	409.2082	205.1077	408.2241	204.6157	P	1205.6749	603.3411	1188.6484	594.8278	1187.6644	594.3358	11
5	513.2667	257.1370	496.2402	248.6237	495.2562	248.1317	S	1108.6222	554.8147	1091.5956	546.3014	1090.6116	545.8094	10
6	614.3144	307.6608	597.2879	299.1476	596.3039	298.6556	T	1021.5901	511.2987	1004.5636	502.7854	1003.5796	502.2934	9
7	671.3359	336.1716	654.3093	327.6583	653.3253	327.1663	G	920.5425	460.7749	903.5159	452.2616			8
8	728.3573	364.6823	711.3308	356.1690	710.3468	355.6770	G	863.5210	432.2641	846.4944	423.7509			7
9	827.4258	414.2165	810.3992	405.7032	809.4152	405.2112	V	806.4995	403.7534	789.4730	395.2401			6
10	997.5313	499.2693	980.5047	490.7560	979.5207	490.2640	K	707.4311	354.2192	690.4046	345.7059			5
11	1125.6263	563.3168	1108.5997	554.8035	1107.6157	554.3115	K	537.3256	269.1664	520.2990	260.6532			4
12	1222.6790	611.8431	1205.6525	603.3299	1204.6684	602.8379	P	409.2306	205.1190	392.2041	196.6057			3
13	1359.7379	680.3726	1342.7114	671.8593	1341.7274	671.3673	H	312.1779	156.5926	295.1513	148.0793			2
14							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KSAPSTGGVKKPHR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
22.2	1532.8423	0.0001	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
14.8	1532.8423	0.0001	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
11.2	1532.8384	0.0039	KLVYGICRKEK
8.7	1532.8351	0.0073	GLSKFVWEGKANK
8.7	1532.8351	0.0073	GLSKFVWEGKANK
8.6	1532.8450	-0.0026	KSAITKNLLDFV
8.4	1532.8418	0.0006	LESAKLCKEIMR
7.6	1532.8384	0.0039	TPMAFKEINSRK
7.6	1532.8384	0.0039	TPMAFKEINSRK
7.4	1532.8423	0.0001	SRAKSNASFKGLR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KSAPSTGGVKKPHR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 60896: 1532.877672 from(511.966500,3+) intensity(9376.7949) scans(739) rawscans(sn739) rtinseconds(587.6734) index(137312)

Title: 525: Scan 739 (rt=9.79456) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25249.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: Home, Search, Back, Forward, Zoom In, Zoom Out, and a search range box set to 75.17 to 947.45.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1532.8787

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K1 : Acetyl (K)

K10 : Methyl (K)

K11 : Methyl (K)

R14 : Methyl (R)

Ions Score: 37 Expect: 0.023

Matches : 14/138 fragment ions using 26 most intense peaks (help)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ⁺⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ⁺⁺⁺	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							14
2	258.1448	129.5761	241.1183	121.0628	240.1343	120.5708	S	1363.7805	682.3939	1346.7539	673.8806	1345.7699	673.3886	13
3	329.1819	165.0946	312.1554	156.5813	311.1714	156.0893	A	1276.7484	638.8779	1259.7219	630.3646	1258.7379	629.8726	12
4	426.2347	213.6210	409.2082	205.1077	408.2241	204.6157	P	1205.7113	603.3593	1188.6848	594.8460	1187.7008	594.3540	11
5	513.2667	257.1370	496.2402	248.6237	495.2562	248.1317	S	1108.6586	554.8329	1091.6320	546.3196	1090.6480	545.8276	10
6	614.3144	307.6608	597.2879	299.1476	596.3039	298.6556	T	1021.6265	511.3169	1004.6000	502.8036	1003.6160	502.3116	9
7	671.3359	336.1716	654.3093	327.6583	653.3253	327.1663	G	920.5788	460.7931	903.5523	452.2798			8
8	728.3573	364.6823	711.3308	356.1690	710.3468	355.6770	G	863.5574	432.2823	846.5308	423.7691			7
9	827.4258	414.2165	810.3992	405.7032	809.4152	405.2112	V	806.5359	403.7716	789.5094	395.2583			6
10	969.5364	485.2718	952.5098	476.7585	951.5258	476.2665	K	707.4675	354.2374	690.4410	345.7241			5
11	1111.6470	556.3271	1094.6204	547.8139	1093.6364	547.3218	K	565.3569	283.1821	548.3303	274.6688			4
12	1208.6997	604.8535	1191.6732	596.3402	1190.6892	595.8482	P	423.2463	212.1268	406.2197	203.6135			3
13	1345.7587	673.3830	1328.7321	664.8697	1327.7481	664.3777	H	326.1935	163.6004	309.1670	155.0871			2
14							R	189.1346	95.0709	172.1081	86.5577			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KSAPSTGGVKKPHR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
37.1	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
27.3	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
27.2	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
27.2	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
27.1	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
20.8	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
20.8	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
20.8	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
20.8	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR
20.8	1532.8787	-0.0010	KSAPSTGGVKKPHR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **YKPGTVALR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 20267: 1045.592128 from(523.803340,2+) intensity(18360.2930) scans(4111) rawscans(sn4111) rtinseconds(1539.4178) index(89810)

Title: 3356: Scan 4111 (rt=25.657) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25241.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Range: 58.18 to 945.31

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1045.5920

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K2 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 23 **Expect:** 0.062

Matches : 16/78 fragment ions using 33 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	164.0706	82.5389					Y							9
2	334.1761	167.5917	317.1496	159.0784			K	883.5360	442.2716	866.5094	433.7584	865.5254	433.2663	8
3	431.2289	216.1181	414.2023	207.6048			P	713.4305	357.2189	696.4039	348.7056	695.4199	348.2136	7
4	488.2504	244.6288	471.2238	236.1155			G	616.3777	308.6925	599.3511	300.1792	598.3671	299.6872	6
5	589.2980	295.1527	572.2715	286.6394	571.2875	286.1474	T	559.3562	280.1817	542.3297	271.6685	541.3457	271.1765	5
6	688.3665	344.6869	671.3399	336.1736	670.3559	335.6816	V	458.3085	229.6579	441.2820	221.1446			4
7	759.4036	380.2054	742.3770	371.6921	741.3930	371.2001	A	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104			3
8	872.4876	436.7475	855.4611	428.2342	854.4771	427.7422	L	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
9							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [YKPGTVALR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
23.0	1045.5920	0.0001	YKPGTVALR
9.5	1045.5936	-0.0015	YKKSSKK
9.5	1045.5936	-0.0015	YKKSSKK
8.7	1045.5880	0.0041	NRTKDDKK
7.8	1045.5920	0.0001	KYSRIAPK
5.7	1045.5920	0.0001	FADGKAVLR
5.2	1045.5880	0.0041	SSLRSPTSR
4.8	1045.5936	-0.0015	YKKSSKK
4.8	1045.5936	-0.0015	YKKSSKK
4.5	1045.5880	0.0042	NSKKRSSK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **YKPGTVALR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 23282: 1083.549768 from(542.782160,2+) intensity(24354.3070) scans(2978) rawscans(sn2978) rtinseconds(1191.549) index(126366)

Title: 2440: Scan 2978 (rt=19.8592) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25247.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, zoom reset, search box (75.18 to 893.3), zoom in, right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1083.5478

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

T5 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 34 **Expect:** 0.0098

Matches : 14/126 fragment ions using 20 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	164.0706	82.5389					Y							9
2	292.1656	146.5864	275.1390	138.0731			K	921.4917	461.2495	904.4652	452.7362	903.4812	452.2442	8
3	389.2183	195.1128	372.1918	186.5995			P	793.3968	397.2020	776.3702	388.6888	775.3862	388.1967	7
4	446.2398	223.6235	429.2132	215.1103			G	696.3440	348.6756	679.3175	340.1624	678.3335	339.6704	6
5	627.2538	314.1305	610.2273	305.6173	609.2432	305.1253	T	639.3226	320.1649	622.2960	311.6516	621.3120	311.1596	5
6	726.3222	363.6647	709.2957	355.1515	708.3117	354.6595	V	458.3085	229.6579	441.2820	221.1446			4
7	797.3593	399.1833	780.3328	390.6700	779.3488	390.1780	A	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104			3
8	910.4434	455.7253	893.4168	447.2121	892.4328	446.7201	L	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
9							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [YKPGTVALR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
33.9	1083.5478	0.0020	YKPGTVALR
11.7	1083.5511	-0.0013	MLSARSAIK
9.0	1083.5518	-0.0020	WPFKSALK
7.2	1083.5511	-0.0014	PRSSKSMK
6.5	1083.5511	-0.0014	KGMKSEIR
5.8	1083.5478	0.0020	FINTALLGR
5.8	1083.5550	-0.0052	RSSSSLRR
5.0	1083.5457	0.0041	YKMVDGVMK
4.6	1083.5511	-0.0013	MLSARSAIK
4.3	1083.5511	-0.0014	PRSSKSMK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **FQKSTELLIR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 37347: 1275.718108 from(638.866330,2+) intensity(264040.9400) scans(7610) rawscans(sn7610) rtinseconds(2547.3091) index(106035)

Title: 6226: Scan 7610 (rt=42.4552) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25243.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1275.7187

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K3 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 86 Expect: 2.9e-07

Matches : 17/92 fragment ions using 18 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	148.0757	74.5415					F							10
2	276.1343	138.5708	259.1077	130.0575			Q	1129.6575	565.3324	1112.6310	556.8191	1111.6470	556.3271	9
3	446.2398	223.6235	429.2132	215.1103			K	1001.5990	501.3031	984.5724	492.7898	983.5884	492.2978	8
4	533.2718	267.1396	516.2453	258.6263	515.2613	258.1343	S	831.4934	416.2504	814.4669	407.7371	813.4829	407.2451	7
5	634.3195	317.6634	617.2930	309.1501	616.3089	308.6581	T	744.4614	372.7343	727.4349	364.2211	726.4509	363.7291	6
6	763.3621	382.1847	746.3355	373.6714	745.3515	373.1794	E	643.4137	322.2105	626.3872	313.6972	625.4032	313.2052	5
7	876.4462	438.7267	859.4196	430.2134	858.4356	429.7214	L	514.3711	257.6892	497.3446	249.1759			4
8	989.5302	495.2688	972.5037	486.7555	971.5197	486.2635	L	401.2871	201.1472	384.2605	192.6339			3
9	1102.6143	551.8108	1085.5877	543.2975	1084.6037	542.8055	I	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
10							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [FOKSTELLIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
85.8	1275.7187	-0.0006	FOKSTELLIR
39.9	1275.7146	0.0035	LSSISQKSRSK
24.8	1275.7146	0.0035	SSLSNKTARSK
24.8	1275.7146	0.0035	SSLSNKTARSK
24.5	1275.7146	0.0035	SSERNKSKDK
21.4	1275.7146	0.0035	SSERNKSKDK
21.4	1275.7146	0.0035	SSERNKSKDK
21.2	1275.7186	-0.0005	SLSPKYLKTR
21.0	1275.7186	-0.0005	SSIKNWSDKK
19.6	1275.7187	-0.0006	SSIKNWSDKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **FQKSTELLIR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 40885: 1313.675108 from(657.844830,2+) intensity(8211.1826) scans(5603) rawscans(sn5603) rtinseconds(1861.8676) index(34984)

Title: 4678: Scan 5603 (rt=31.0311) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25233.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Zoom In Zoom Out Search 99.2 to 1240.54

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1313.6744

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

S4 : Phospho (ST), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 97.9769

Ions Score: 53 Expect: 0.00047

Matches : 21/146 fragment ions using 20 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	148.0757	74.5415					F							10
2	276.1343	138.5708	259.1077	130.0575			Q	1167.6133	584.3103	1150.5868	575.7970	1149.6028	575.3050	9
3	404.2292	202.6183	387.2027	194.1050			K	1039.5547	520.2810	1022.5282	511.7677	1021.5442	511.2757	8
4	571.2276	286.1174	554.2010	277.6042	553.2170	277.1122	S	911.4598	456.2335	894.4332	447.7203	893.4492	447.2282	7
5	672.2753	336.6413	655.2487	328.1280	654.2647	327.6360	T	744.4614	372.7343	727.4349	364.2211	726.4509	363.7291	6
6	801.3179	401.1626	784.2913	392.6493	783.3073	392.1573	E	643.4137	322.2105	626.3872	313.6972	625.4032	313.2052	5
7	914.4019	457.7046	897.3754	449.1913	896.3914	448.6993	L	514.3711	257.6892	497.3446	249.1759			4
8	1027.4860	514.2466	1010.4594	505.7334	1009.4754	505.2414	L	401.2871	201.1472	384.2605	192.6339			3
9	1140.5701	570.7887	1123.5435	562.2754	1122.5595	561.7834	I	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
10							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [FOKSTELLIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
52.9	1313.6744	0.0007	FOKSTELLIR	Phospho S4 94.12%
40.8	1313.6744	0.0007	FOKSTELLIR	Phospho T5 5.88%
20.2	1313.6778	-0.0027	SIMKQOTKTK	
17.7	1313.6744	0.0007	NKGTKYPGATK	
17.4	1313.6744	0.0007	NKGTKYPGATK	
17.4	1313.6745	0.0007	QFKVVDGGSKK	
17.0	1313.6704	0.0047	LSSISQKSRSK	
15.5	1313.6704	0.0047	LSSISQKSRSK	
15.2	1313.6778	-0.0027	SIMKQOTKTK	
15.2	1313.6744	0.0007	SLSPKYLKTR	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **EIAQDFKTDLR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 43399: 1348.698328 from(675.356440,2+) intensity(16275.3450) scans(5045) rawscans(sn5045) rtinseconds(1701.9898) index(77201)

Title: 4176: Scan 5045 (rt=28.3665) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25239.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1348.6987

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K7 : Methyl (K)

Ions Score: 62 Expect: 5e-05

Matches : 15/110 fragment ions using 20 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	E							11
2	243.1339	122.0706			225.1234	113.0653	I	1220.6634	610.8353	1203.6368	602.3220	1202.6528	601.8300	10
3	314.1710	157.5892			296.1605	148.5839	A	1107.5793	554.2933	1090.5528	545.7800	1089.5687	545.2880	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	Q	1036.5422	518.7747	1019.5156	510.2615	1018.5316	509.7694	8
5	557.2566	279.1319	540.2300	270.6186	539.2460	270.1266	D	908.4836	454.7454	891.4571	446.2322	890.4730	445.7402	7
6	704.3250	352.6661	687.2984	344.1529	686.3144	343.6608	F	793.4567	397.2320	776.4301	388.7187	775.4461	388.2267	6
7	846.4356	423.7214	829.4090	415.2082	828.4250	414.7162	K	646.3883	323.6978	629.3617	315.1845	628.3777	314.6925	5
8	947.4833	474.2453	930.4567	465.7320	929.4727	465.2400	T	504.2776	252.6425	487.2511	244.1292	486.2671	243.6372	4
9	1062.5102	531.7587	1045.4837	523.2455	1044.4997	522.7535	D	403.2300	202.1186	386.2034	193.6053	385.2194	193.1133	3
10	1175.5943	588.3008	1158.5677	579.7875	1157.5837	579.2955	L	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
11							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [EIAQDFKTDLR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
62.3	1348.6987	-0.0003	EIAQDFKTDLR
15.9	1348.7003	-0.0020	EGASVVKKVVK
13.7	1348.7020	-0.0037	SSLDNCKTAAVK
13.7	1348.7003	-0.0020	SKTPESPKVVK
11.9	1348.7020	-0.0037	SASDKTKLCNK
11.4	1348.6987	-0.0003	EIAQDFKTDLR
11.3	1348.7020	-0.0037	SASDKTKLCNK
10.4	1348.6986	-0.0003	KNIEDEYRVK
10.0	1348.7020	-0.0037	SASDKTKLCNK
10.0	1348.7020	-0.0037	SASDKTKLCNK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **EIAQDFKTDLR**Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 47747: 1376.730492 from(459.917440,3+) intensity(6303.6157) scans(12092) rawscans(sn12092) rtinseconds(3940.7472) index(109444)

Title: 9635: Scan 12092 (rt=65.6791) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25243.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

63.21 to 786.15

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1376.7300

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K7 : Methyl (K)

R11 : Dimethyl (R)

Ions Score: 34 Expect: 0.026

Matches : 18/110 fragment ions using 26 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	E							11
2	243.1339	122.0706			225.1234	113.0653	I	1248.6947	624.8510	1231.6681	616.3377	1230.6841	615.8457	10
3	314.1710	157.5892			296.1605	148.5839	A	1135.6106	568.3089	1118.5841	559.7957	1117.6000	559.3037	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	Q	1064.5735	532.7904	1047.5469	524.2771	1046.5629	523.7851	8
5	557.2566	279.1319	540.2300	270.6186	539.2460	270.1266	D	936.5149	468.7611	919.4884	460.2478	918.5043	459.7558	7
6	704.3250	352.6661	687.2984	344.1529	686.3144	343.6608	F	821.4880	411.2476	804.4614	402.7343	803.4774	402.2423	6
7	846.4356	423.7214	829.4090	415.2082	828.4250	414.7162	K	674.4196	337.7134	657.3930	329.2001	656.4090	328.7081	5
8	947.4833	474.2453	930.4567	465.7320	929.4727	465.2400	T	532.3089	266.6581	515.2824	258.1448	514.2984	257.6528	4
9	1062.5102	531.7587	1045.4837	523.2455	1044.4997	522.7535	D	431.2613	216.1343	414.2347	207.6210	413.2507	207.1290	3
10	1175.5943	588.3008	1158.5677	579.7875	1157.5837	579.2955	L	316.2343	158.6208	299.2078	150.1075			2
11							R	203.1503	102.0788	186.1237	93.5655			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [EIAQDFKTDLR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
33.8	1376.7300	0.0005	EIAQDFKTDLR
30.6	1376.7300	0.0005	EIAQDFKTDLR
23.8	1376.7300	0.0005	EIAQDFKTDLR
15.9	1376.7316	-0.0011	KLPSKVASVEK
11.1	1376.7329	-0.0024	SFSGKKFRSR
10.0	1376.7329	-0.0024	SFSGKKFRSR
10.0	1376.7330	-0.0025	SFSGKKFRSR
9.6	1376.7316	-0.0011	KLAETKPELVK
7.2	1376.7316	-0.0011	KYSKKDTTTK
7.2	1376.7316	-0.0011	KYSKKDTTTK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SEARCH RESULTS

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **EIAQDFKTDLR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 45369: 1362.713908 from(682.364230,2+) intensity(10323.3560) scans(5147) rawscans(sn5147) rtinseconds(1732.086) index(77286)

Title: 4261: Scan 5147 (rt=28.8681) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25239.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

115.31 to 1176.41

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1362.7143

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K7 : Dimethyl (K)

Ions Score: 59 Expect: 0.00011

Matches : 13/110 fragment ions using 18 most intense peaks [\(help\)](#)

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	E							11
2	243.1339	122.0706			225.1234	113.0653	I	1234.6790	617.8431	1217.6525	609.3299	1216.6684	608.8379	10
3	314.1710	157.5892			296.1605	148.5839	A	1121.5949	561.3011	1104.5684	552.7878	1103.5844	552.2958	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	Q	1050.5578	525.7826	1033.5313	517.2693	1032.5473	516.7773	8
5	557.2566	279.1319	540.2300	270.6186	539.2460	270.1266	D	922.4993	461.7533	905.4727	453.2400	904.4887	452.7480	7
6	704.3250	352.6661	687.2984	344.1529	686.3144	343.6608	F	807.4723	404.2398	790.4458	395.7265	789.4617	395.2345	6
7	860.4512	430.7293	843.4247	422.2160	842.4407	421.7240	K	660.4039	330.7056	643.3774	322.1923	642.3933	321.7003	5
8	961.4989	481.2531	944.4724	472.7398	943.4884	472.2478	T	504.2776	252.6425	487.2511	244.1292	486.2671	243.6372	4
9	1076.5259	538.7666	1059.4993	530.2533	1058.5153	529.7613	D	403.2300	202.1186	386.2034	193.6053	385.2194	193.1133	3
10	1189.6099	595.3086	1172.5834	586.7953	1171.5994	586.3033	L	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
11							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [EIAQDFKTDLR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
58.5	1362.7143	-0.0004	EIAQDFKTDLR
15.3	1362.7177	-0.0038	SSLDNCKTAAVK
13.0	1362.7143	-0.0004	LKGDDYNELVR
11.7	1362.7177	-0.0038	SASDKTKLCNK
11.1	1362.7177	-0.0038	SASDKTKLCNK
11.1	1362.7177	-0.0037	NNKTTEAKMSK
11.1	1362.7177	-0.0037	NNKTTEAKMSK
10.5	1362.7160	-0.0021	KYSKKDTTK
10.4	1362.7159	-0.0020	EKKPSAKEVK
10.1	1362.7159	-0.0020	EKKPSAKEVK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **EIAQDFKTDLR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 47779: 1376.730522 from(459.917450,3+) intensity(9033.6123) scans(11810) rawscans(sn11810) rtinseconds(3659.4635) index(119727)

Title: 9515: Scan 11810 (rt=60.991) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25245.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1376.7300
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K7 : Dimethyl (K)
 R11 : Methyl (R)
 Ions Score: 28 Expect: 0.16 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	E							11
2	243.1339	122.0706			225.1234	113.0653	I	1248.6947	624.8510	1231.6681	616.3377	1230.6841	615.8457	10
3	314.1710	157.5892			296.1605	148.5839	A	1135.6106	568.3089	1118.5841	559.7957	1117.6000	559.3037	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	Q	1064.5735	532.7904	1047.5469	524.2771	1046.5629	523.7851	8
5	557.2566	279.1319	540.2300	270.6186	539.2460	270.1266	D	936.5149	468.7611	919.4884	460.2478	918.5043	459.7558	7
6	704.3250	352.6661	687.2984	344.1529	686.3144	343.6608	F	821.4880	411.2476	804.4614	402.7343	803.4774	402.2423	6
7	860.4512	430.7293	843.4247	422.2160	842.4407	421.7240	K	674.4196	337.7134	657.3930	329.2001	656.4090	328.7081	5
8	961.4989	481.2531	944.4724	472.7398	943.4884	472.2478	T	518.2933	259.6503	501.2667	251.1370	500.2827	250.6450	4
9	1076.5259	538.7666	1059.4993	530.2533	1058.5153	529.7613	D	417.2456	209.1264	400.2191	200.6132	399.2350	200.1212	3
10	1189.6099	595.3086	1172.5834	586.7953	1171.5994	586.3033	L	302.2187	151.6130	285.1921	143.0997			2
11							R	189.1346	95.0709	172.1081	86.5577			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [EIAQDFKTDLR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
27.6	1376.7300	0.0006	EIAQDFKTDLR
21.4	1376.7299	0.0006	EQNAKIYNTLK
21.0	1376.7300	0.0006	EIAQDFKTDLR
16.5	1376.7300	0.0006	EIAQDFKTDLR
16.5	1376.7316	-0.0011	KLAETKPELVK
16.0	1376.7316	-0.0011	KLAETKPELVK
14.1	1376.7299	0.0006	AEIQQYKENLK
12.9	1376.7316	-0.0011	EIAKLTQPSLK
9.3	1376.7259	0.0046	RATSTSKGSEQK
9.3	1376.7259	0.0046	RATSTSKGSEQK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MASCOT SEARCH RESULTS

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **EIAQDFKTDLR**

Found in **H3_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P61830|H3_YEAST Histone H3 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHT1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 46862: 1376.729888 from(689.372220,2+) intensity(5558.0596) scans(8130) rawscans(sn8130) rtinseconds(2557.2812) index(116930)

Title: 6718: Scan 8130 (rt=42.6214) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25245.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\533 Final H3 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

to

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1376.7300
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K7 : Trimethyl (K), with neutral losses 0.0000(shown in table), 59.0735
 Ions Score: 29 Expect: 0.03
 Matches : 10/170 fragment ions using 18 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	E							11
2	243.1339	122.0706			225.1234	113.0653	I	1248.6947	624.8510	1231.6681	616.3377	1230.6841	615.8457	10
3	314.1710	157.5892			296.1605	148.5839	A	1135.6106	568.3089	1118.5841	559.7957	1117.6000	559.3037	9
4	442.2296	221.6185	425.2031	213.1052	424.2191	212.6132	Q	1064.5735	532.7904	1047.5469	524.2771	1046.5629	523.7851	8
5	557.2566	279.1319	540.2300	270.6186	539.2460	270.1266	D	936.5149	468.7611	919.4884	460.2478	918.5043	459.7558	7
6	704.3250	352.6661	687.2984	344.1529	686.3144	343.6608	F	821.4880	411.2476	804.4614	402.7343	803.4774	402.2423	6
7	874.4669	437.7371	857.4403	429.2238	856.4563	428.7318	K	674.4196	337.7134	657.3930	329.2001	656.4090	328.7081	5
8	975.5146	488.2609	958.4880	479.7477	957.5040	479.2556	T	504.2776	252.6425	487.2511	244.1292	486.2671	243.6372	4
9	1090.5415	545.7744	1073.5150	537.2611	1072.5310	536.7691	D	403.2300	202.1186	386.2034	193.6053	385.2194	193.1133	3
10	1203.6256	602.3164	1186.5990	593.8032	1185.6150	593.3111	L	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
11							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [EIAQDFKTDLR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
29.0	1376.7300	-0.0001	EIAQDFKTDLR
11.9	1376.7267	0.0032	MKKQLKTTK
11.9	1376.7347	-0.0048	MRRFRSSSHSLK
11.9	1376.7300	-0.0001	PTYINLTDATLR
11.9	1376.7251	0.0048	SGHMAKCLKELK
11.9	1376.7251	0.0048	SGHMAKCLKELK
11.9	1376.7251	0.0048	SGHMAKCLKELK
11.9	1376.7316	-0.0017	LDLKPENASLK
11.8	1376.7333	-0.0034	MKSDDSRDLIK
11.8	1376.7333	-0.0034	SSLDNCKTAAVK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 99335: 1595.873028 from(798.943790,2+) intensity(5865.8413) scans(2807) rawscans(sn2807)

rtinseconds(1125.3195) index(19387)

Title: 2260: Scan 2807 (rt=18.7553) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25410.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? (help), image (download), left arrow, zoom in, zoom out, zoom reset, search box (125.99 to 1550.76), zoom in, right arrow.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1595.8743

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

N-term : Acetyl (Protein N-term)

R3 : Methyl (R)

K5 : Acetyl (K)

K8 : Acetyl (K)

K12 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 45 **Expect:** 0.0013

Matches : 17/146 fragment ions using 36 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	#
1	130.0499	65.5286			112.0393	56.5233	S					16
2	187.0713	94.0393			169.0608	85.0340	G	1467.8390	734.4232	1450.8125	725.9099	15
3	357.1881	179.0977	340.1615	170.5844	339.1775	170.0924	R	1410.8176	705.9124	1393.7910	697.3992	14
4	414.2096	207.6084	397.1830	199.0951	396.1990	198.6031	G	1240.7008	620.8540	1223.6743	612.3408	13
5	584.3151	292.6612	567.2885	284.1479	566.3045	283.6559	K	1183.6794	592.3433	1166.6528	583.8300	12
6	641.3365	321.1719	624.3100	312.6586	623.3260	312.1666	G	1013.5738	507.2905	996.5473	498.7773	11
7	698.3580	349.6826	681.3315	341.1694	680.3474	340.6774	G	956.5524	478.7798	939.5258	470.2665	10
8	868.4635	434.7354	851.4370	426.2221	850.4530	425.7301	K	899.5309	450.2691	882.5043	441.7558	9
9	925.4850	463.2461	908.4585	454.7329	907.4744	454.2409	G	729.4254	365.2163	712.3988	356.7030	8

10	1038.5691	519.7882	1021.5425	511.2749	1020.5585	510.7829	L	672.4039	336.7056	655.3774	328.1923	7
11	1095.5905	548.2989	1078.5640	539.7856	1077.5800	539.2936	G	559.3198	280.1636	542.2933	271.6503	6
12	1265.6961	633.3517	1248.6695	624.8384	1247.6855	624.3464	K	502.2984	251.6528	485.2718	243.1396	5
13	1322.7175	661.8624	1305.6910	653.3491	1304.7070	652.8571	G	332.1928	166.6001	315.1663	158.0868	4
14	1379.7390	690.3731	1362.7124	681.8599	1361.7284	681.3679	G	275.1714	138.0893	258.1448	129.5761	3
15	1450.7761	725.8917	1433.7496	717.3784	1432.7655	716.8864	A	218.1499	109.5786	201.1234	101.0653	2
16							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468	1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calcd)	Delta	Sequence	Site Analysis
44.6	1595.8743	-0.0013	SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK	Methyl R3, Acetyl N-term, K5, K8, K12; 97.44%
28.0	1595.8743	-0.0013	SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK	Methyl R3, Acetyl N-term, K5, K8, K16; 2.10%
12.9	1595.8783	-0.0053	APDLERWREGIIK	
10.8	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
10.6	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
10.2	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
9.9	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
9.9	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
9.7	1595.8760	-0.0029	KKLSKKNNGSGSGNK	
8.7	1595.8760	-0.0030	SVVKTDDGKTRLR	

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **GKGGKGLGKGGAKR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 86140: 1437.804028 from(719.909290,2+) intensity(25900.0740) scans(3111) rawscans(sn3111) rtinseconds(1204.3071) index(2501)

Title: 2502: Scan 3111 (rt=20.0718) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25408.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search Zoom In Zoom Out Full Screen 128.29 to 1364.65

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1437.8052
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

- K2 : Acetyl (K)
- K5 : Acetyl (K)
- K9 : Acetyl (K)
- K13 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 117 Expect: 2.7e-10

Matches : 29/102 fragment ions using 28 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	#
1	58.0287	29.5180			G					14
2	228.1343	114.5708	211.1077	106.0575	K	1381.7910	691.3992	1364.7645	682.8859	13
3	285.1557	143.0815	268.1292	134.5682	G	1211.6855	606.3464	1194.6589	597.8331	12
4	342.1772	171.5922	325.1506	163.0790	G	1154.6640	577.8357	1137.6375	569.3224	11
5	512.2827	256.6450	495.2562	248.1317	K	1097.6426	549.3249	1080.6160	540.8116	10
6	569.3042	285.1557	552.2776	276.6425	G	927.5370	464.2722	910.5105	455.7589	9
7	682.3883	341.6978	665.3617	333.1845	L	870.5156	435.7614	853.4890	427.2482	8
8	739.4097	370.2085	722.3832	361.6952	G	757.4315	379.2194	740.4050	370.7061	7
9	909.5152	455.2613	892.4887	446.7480	K	700.4101	350.7087	683.3835	342.1954	6
10	966.5367	483.7720	949.5102	475.2587	G	530.3045	265.6559	513.2780	257.1426	5

11	1023.5582	512.2827	1006.5316	503.7694	G	473.2831	237.1452	456.2565	228.6319	4
12	1094.5953	547.8013	1077.5687	539.2880	A	416.2616	208.6344	399.2350	200.1212	3
13	1264.7008	632.8540	1247.6743	624.3408	K	345.2245	173.1159	328.1979	164.6026	2
14					R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498	1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [GKGGKGLGKGGAKR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
117.3	1437.8052	-0.0011	GKGGKGLGKGGAKR
32.6	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK
24.0	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK
23.4	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK
21.7	1437.8030	0.0011	ACLKELKKS
21.7	1437.8030	0.0011	ACLKELKKS
21.3	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK
21.1	1437.8051	-0.0011	NKKGKNRNNK
20.8	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK
20.8	1437.8068	-0.0028	GKSSKKRASKK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **GKGGKGLGKGGAKR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 83189: 1409.808552 from(470.943460,3+) intensity(31009.3130) scans(1967) rawscans(sn1967) rtinseconds(875.9551) index(141458)

Title: 1585: Scan 1967 (rt=14.5993) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25426.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Search Back Forward 75.1 to 981.48

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1409.8103

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K2 : Acetyl (K)

K5 : Methyl (K)

K9 : Acetyl (K)

K13 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 28 Expect: 0.14 ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	#
1	58.0287	29.5180			G					14
2	228.1343	114.5708	211.1077	106.0575	K	1353.7961	677.4017	1336.7696	668.8884	13
3	285.1557	143.0815	268.1292	134.5682	G	1183.6906	592.3489	1166.6640	583.8357	12
4	342.1772	171.5922	325.1506	163.0790	G	1126.6691	563.8382	1109.6426	555.3249	11
5	484.2878	242.6475	467.2613	234.1343	K	1069.6477	535.3275	1052.6211	526.8142	10
6	541.3093	271.1583	524.2827	262.6450	G	927.5370	464.2722	910.5105	455.7589	9
7	654.3933	327.7003	637.3668	319.1870	L	870.5156	435.7614	853.4890	427.2482	8
8	711.4148	356.2110	694.3883	347.6978	G	757.4315	379.2194	740.4050	370.7061	7
9	881.5203	441.2638	864.4938	432.7505	K	700.4101	350.7087	683.3835	342.1954	6
10	938.5418	469.7745	921.5152	461.2613	G	530.3045	265.6559	513.2780	257.1426	5

11	995.5633	498.2853	978.5367	489.7720	G	473.2831	237.1452	456.2565	228.6319	4
12	1066.6004	533.8038	1049.5738	525.2905	A	416.2616	208.6344	399.2350	200.1212	3
13	1236.7059	618.8566	1219.6794	610.3433	K	345.2245	173.1159	328.1979	164.6026	2
14					R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498	1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [GKGGKGLGKGGAKR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
27.8	1409.8103	-0.0017	GKGGKGLGKGGAKR
22.0	1409.8103	-0.0017	GKGGKGLGKGGAKR
17.4	1409.8103	-0.0017	KAGGKGLGKGGKGR
12.5	1409.8132	-0.0047	RFKKIRSRR
11.3	1409.8103	-0.0017	KAGGKGLGKGGKGR
11.3	1409.8119	-0.0033	GKSSKKRASKK
11.3	1409.8119	-0.0033	GKSSKKRASKK
11.3	1409.8119	-0.0033	GKSSKKRASKK
11.3	1409.8119	-0.0033	GKSSKKRASKK
10.7	1409.8119	-0.0033	KSARKKSSKGK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **GKGGKGLKGGAKR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 87687: 1451.820588 from(726.917570,2+) intensity(22661.0760) scans(3492) rawscans(sn3492) rtinseconds(1239.0236) index(82259)

Title: 2908: Scan 3492 (rt=20.6504) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25418.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

185.21 to 1378.54

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1451.8208

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K2 : Acetyl (K)

K5 : Acetyl (K)

K9 : Acetyl (K)

K13 : Acetyl (K)

R14 : Methyl (R)

Ions Score: 43 Expect: 0.0074

Matches : 17/102 fragment ions using 35 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	#
1	58.0287	29.5180			G					14
2	228.1343	114.5708	211.1077	106.0575	K	1395.8067	698.4070	1378.7801	689.8937	13
3	285.1557	143.0815	268.1292	134.5682	G	1225.7011	613.3542	1208.6746	604.8409	12
4	342.1772	171.5922	325.1506	163.0790	G	1168.6797	584.8435	1151.6531	576.3302	11
5	512.2827	256.6450	495.2562	248.1317	K	1111.6582	556.3327	1094.6317	547.8195	10
6	569.3042	285.1557	552.2776	276.6425	G	941.5527	471.2800	924.5261	462.7667	9
7	682.3883	341.6978	665.3617	333.1845	L	884.5312	442.7693	867.5047	434.2560	8
8	739.4097	370.2085	722.3832	361.6952	G	771.4472	386.2272	754.4206	377.7139	7
9	909.5152	455.2613	892.4887	446.7480	K	714.4257	357.7165	697.3992	349.2032	6

10	966.5367	483.7720	949.5102	475.2587	G	544.3202	272.6637	527.2936	264.1504	5
11	1023.5582	512.2827	1006.5316	503.7694	G	487.2987	244.1530	470.2722	235.6397	4
12	1094.5953	547.8013	1077.5687	539.2880	A	430.2772	215.6423	413.2507	207.1290	3
13	1264.7008	632.8540	1247.6743	624.3408	K	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104	2
14					R	189.1346	95.0709	172.1081	86.5577	1

NCBI BLAST search of [GKGGKGLGKGGAKR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
43.0	1451.8208	-0.0002	GKGGKGLGKGGAKR
22.9	1451.8208	-0.0002	NGKKGKAKQKR
18.4	1451.8225	-0.0019	KKGKSSNGGNK
18.4	1451.8225	-0.0019	KKGKSSNGGNK
17.2	1451.8208	-0.0002	NKKGKNRKK
17.1	1451.8225	-0.0019	KKGKSSNGGNK
17.1	1451.8225	-0.0019	KKGKSSNGGNK
16.0	1451.8265	-0.0059	ERIKFKPSK
15.9	1451.8160	0.0046	CKKVIKRTVGR
15.9	1451.8160	0.0046	CKKVIKRTVGR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **DNIQGITKPAIR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c)
GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 77200: 1366.756668 from(684.385610,2+) intensity(40341.5230) scans(6268) rawscans(sn6268) rtinseconds(2039.3151)
index(84583)

Title: 5232: Scan 6268 (rt=33.9886) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25418.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

111.98 to 1293.59

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1366.7568

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K8 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 62 Expect: 8.2e-05

Matches : 22/120 fragment ions using 31 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	116.0342	58.5207			98.0237	49.5155	D							12
2	230.0771	115.5422	213.0506	107.0289	212.0666	106.5369	N	1252.7372	626.8722	1235.7106	618.3590	1234.7266	617.8670	11
3	343.1612	172.0842	326.1347	163.5710	325.1506	163.0790	I	1138.6943	569.8508	1121.6677	561.3375	1120.6837	560.8455	10
4	471.2198	236.1135	454.1932	227.6003	453.2092	227.1082	Q	1025.6102	513.3087	1008.5837	504.7955	1007.5996	504.3035	9
5	528.2413	264.6243	511.2147	256.1110	510.2307	255.6190	G	897.5516	449.2795	880.5251	440.7662	879.5411	440.2742	8
6	641.3253	321.1663	624.2988	312.6530	623.3148	312.1610	I	840.5302	420.7687	823.5036	412.2554	822.5196	411.7634	7
7	742.3730	371.6901	725.3464	363.1769	724.3624	362.6849	T	727.4461	364.2267	710.4196	355.7134	709.4355	355.2214	6
8	912.4785	456.7429	895.4520	448.2296	894.4680	447.7376	K	626.3984	313.7028	609.3719	305.1896			5
9	1009.5313	505.2693	992.5047	496.7560	991.5207	496.2640	P	456.2929	228.6501	439.2663	220.1368			4
10	1080.5684	540.7878	1063.5419	532.2746	1062.5578	531.7826	A	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104			3
11	1193.6525	597.3299	1176.6259	588.8166	1175.6419	588.3246	I	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
12							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [DNIQGITKPAIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
62.1	1366.7568	-0.0002	DNIQGITKPAIR
27.8	1366.7585	-0.0018	KGKKSEKKS
24.7	1366.7585	-0.0018	SKKGKKSEK
18.8	1366.7568	-0.0002	NDIAQVPKNANK
18.7	1366.7585	-0.0018	KTATSKPGGSK
18.7	1366.7585	-0.0018	KTATSKPGGSK
18.2	1366.7520	0.0047	MIKRSLASLVR
16.4	1366.7585	-0.0018	KKKTVKESNK
16.4	1366.7585	-0.0018	KKKTVKESNK
16.4	1366.7585	-0.0018	SKKGKKSEK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **DNIQGITKPAIR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 74987: 1352.776708 from(677.395630,2+) intensity(14573.0800) scans(5257) rawscans(sn5257) rtinseconds(1684.8249) index(127975)

Title: 4494: Scan 5257 (rt=28.0804) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25424.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 106.02 to 1280.32

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1352.7776
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K8 : Dimethyl (K)
 Ions Score: 29 Expect: 0.13
 Matches : 15/120 fragment ions using 28 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b*	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	116.0342	58.5207			98.0237	49.5155	D							12
2	230.0771	115.5422	213.0506	107.0289	212.0666	106.5369	N	1238.7579	619.8826	1221.7314	611.3693	1220.7474	610.8773	11
3	343.1612	172.0842	326.1347	163.5710	325.1506	163.0790	I	1124.7150	562.8611	1107.6885	554.3479	1106.7044	553.8559	10
4	471.2198	236.1135	454.1932	227.6003	453.2092	227.1082	Q	1011.6309	506.3191	994.6044	497.8058	993.6204	497.3138	9
5	528.2413	264.6243	511.2147	256.1110	510.2307	255.6190	G	883.5724	442.2898	866.5458	433.7765	865.5618	433.2845	8
6	641.3253	321.1663	624.2988	312.6530	623.3148	312.1610	I	826.5509	413.7791	809.5244	405.2658	808.5403	404.7738	7
7	742.3730	371.6901	725.3464	363.1769	724.3624	362.6849	T	713.4668	357.2371	696.4403	348.7238	695.4563	348.2318	6
8	898.4993	449.7533	881.4727	441.2400	880.4887	440.7480	K	612.4192	306.7132	595.3926	298.1999			5
9	995.5520	498.2796	978.5255	489.7664	977.5415	489.2744	P	456.2929	228.6501	439.2663	220.1368			4
10	1066.5891	533.7982	1049.5626	525.2849	1048.5786	524.7929	A	359.2401	180.1237	342.2136	171.6104			3
11	1179.6732	590.3402	1162.6467	581.8270	1161.6626	581.3350	I	288.2030	144.6051	271.1765	136.0919			2
12							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [DNIQGITKPAIR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
29.5	1352.7776	-0.0009	DNIQGITKPAIR
26.1	1352.7776	-0.0009	DNIQGITKPAIR
20.8	1352.7776	-0.0009	DNIQGITKPAIR
18.2	1352.7792	-0.0025	TKLKKDTKKK
15.6	1352.7792	-0.0025	TKLKKDTKKK
15.3	1352.7792	-0.0025	TKLKKDTKKK
14.6	1352.7776	-0.0009	GISVPGTKDPGKR
11.4	1352.7776	-0.0009	GISVPGTKDPGKR
11.4	1352.7776	-0.0009	GISVPGTKDPGKR
11.0	1352.7792	-0.0025	TKLKNKSKSK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **ISGLIYEEVR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 53733: 1205.665688 from(603.840120,2+) intensity(10438.7610) scans(10087) rawscans(sn10087) rtinseconds(3037.4058) index(8447)

Title: 8448: Scan 10087 (rt=50.6234) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25408.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: question mark, home, back, forward, search, zoom in, zoom out, search range (101.18 to 1193.56), search, forward.

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1205.6656
Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
Variable modifications:
 R10 : Dimethyl (R)
Ions Score: 63 **Expect:** 4.5e-05
Matches : 12/84 fragment ions using 16 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	114.0913	57.5493			I							10
2	201.1234	101.0653	183.1128	92.0600	S	1093.5888	547.2980	1076.5623	538.7848	1075.5782	538.2928	9
3	258.1448	129.5761	240.1343	120.5708	G	1006.5568	503.7820	989.5302	495.2688	988.5462	494.7767	8
4	371.2289	186.1181	353.2183	177.1128	L	949.5353	475.2713	932.5088	466.7580	931.5247	466.2660	7
5	484.3130	242.6601	466.3024	233.6548	I	836.4512	418.7293	819.4247	410.2160	818.4407	409.7240	6
6	647.3763	324.1918	629.3657	315.1865	Y	723.3672	362.1872	706.3406	353.6740	705.3566	353.1819	5
7	776.4189	388.7131	758.4083	379.7078	E	560.3039	280.6556	543.2773	272.1423	542.2933	271.6503	4
8	905.4615	453.2344	887.4509	444.2291	E	431.2613	216.1343	414.2347	207.6210	413.2507	207.1290	3
9	1004.5299	502.7686	986.5193	493.7633	V	302.2187	151.6130	285.1921	143.0997			2
10					R	203.1503	102.0788	186.1237	93.5655			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [ISGLIYEEVR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
63.1	1205.6656	0.0001	ISGLIYEEVR
17.0	1205.6655	0.0001	QLELYKSNK
17.0	1205.6655	0.0001	QLELYKSNK
17.0	1205.6656	0.0001	KDLLDYAAQK
15.6	1205.6655	0.0001	QKNYIEELK
12.0	1205.6655	0.0001	LEKEFEQKK
12.0	1205.6655	0.0001	LEKEFEQKK
12.0	1205.6656	0.0001	LEKEFEQKK
10.4	1205.6645	0.0012	RSIPSNKIR
10.0	1205.6689	-0.0033	LGMVAASSTSIK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **DSVTYTEHAKR**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 73923: 1347.640348 from(674.827450,2+) intensity(13994.3370) scans(1876) rawscans(sn1876) rtinseconds(832.2466) index(125048)

Title: 1567: Scan 1876 (rt=13.8708) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25424.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 123.18 to 1274.47

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1347.6419

Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)

Variable modifications:

K10 : Acetyl (K)

Ions Score: 57 Expect: 6.9e-05

Matches : 24/94 fragment ions using 28 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	116.0342	58.5207			98.0237	49.5155	D							11
2	203.0662	102.0368			185.0557	93.0315	S	1233.6222	617.3148	1216.5957	608.8015	1215.6117	608.3095	10
3	302.1347	151.5710			284.1241	142.5657	V	1146.5902	573.7987	1129.5637	565.2855	1128.5796	564.7935	9
4	403.1823	202.0948			385.1718	193.0895	T	1047.5218	524.2645	1030.4952	515.7513	1029.5112	515.2592	8
5	566.2457	283.6265			548.2351	274.6212	Y	946.4741	473.7407	929.4476	465.2274	928.4635	464.7354	7
6	667.2933	334.1503			649.2828	325.1450	T	783.4108	392.2090	766.3842	383.6958	765.4002	383.2037	6
7	796.3359	398.6716			778.3254	389.6663	E	682.3631	341.6852	665.3366	333.1719	664.3525	332.6799	5
8	933.3949	467.2011			915.3843	458.1958	H	553.3205	277.1639	536.2940	268.6506			4
9	1004.4320	502.7196			986.4214	493.7143	A	416.2616	208.6344	399.2350	200.1212			3
10	1174.5375	587.7724	1157.5109	579.2591	1156.5269	578.7671	K	345.2245	173.1159	328.1979	164.6026			2
11							R	175.1190	88.0631	158.0924	79.5498			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [DSVITYTEHA KR](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)**All matches to this query**

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
56.8	1347.6419	-0.0015	DSVITYTEHA KR
11.7	1347.6451	-0.0048	EITKTSKKK
11.3	1347.6353	0.0051	HTPPLNPSKK
10.6	1347.6451	-0.0048	EITKTSKKK
10.4	1347.6340	0.0064	MKNEDEENKK
10.1	1347.6435	-0.0032	ILDPNPESTLR
9.7	1347.6451	-0.0048	IASKSEKTLK
9.7	1347.6451	-0.0048	IASKSEKTLK
9.6	1347.6378	0.0025	TKDAEVNNGSSAR
9.6	1347.6408	-0.0005	SQDRKSHNIR

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **KTVTSLDVVYALK**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 89938: 1477.839948 from(739.927250,2+) intensity(7629.3867) scans(9865) rawscans(sn9865) rtinseconds(2963.6685) index(40642)

Title: 8325: Scan 9865 (rt=49.3945) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25412.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Back Forward Search 135.2 to 1436.44

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide $M_r(\text{calc})$: 1477.8392
 Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
 Variable modifications:
 K1 : Acetyl (K)
 Ions Score: 84 Expect: 7.6e-07
 Matches : 20/130 fragment ions using 23 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b [*]	b ^{*++}	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y [*]	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	171.1128	86.0600	154.0863	77.5468			K							13
2	272.1605	136.5839	255.1339	128.0706	254.1499	127.5786	T	1308.7409	654.8741	1291.7144	646.3608	1290.7304	645.8688	12
3	371.2289	186.1181	354.2023	177.6048	353.2183	177.1128	V	1207.6933	604.3503	1190.6667	595.8370	1189.6827	595.3450	11
4	472.2766	236.6419	455.2500	228.1287	454.2660	227.6366	T	1108.6249	554.8161	1091.5983	546.3028	1090.6143	545.8108	10
5	559.3086	280.1579	542.2821	271.6447	541.2980	271.1527	S	1007.5772	504.2922	990.5506	495.7790	989.5666	495.2869	9
6	672.3927	336.7000	655.3661	328.1867	654.3821	327.6947	L	920.5451	460.7762	903.5186	452.2629	902.5346	451.7709	8
7	787.4196	394.2134	770.3931	385.7002	769.4090	385.2082	D	807.4611	404.2342	790.4345	395.7209	789.4505	395.2289	7
8	886.4880	443.7477	869.4615	435.2344	868.4775	434.7424	V	692.4341	346.7207	675.4076	338.2074			6
9	985.5564	493.2819	968.5299	484.7686	967.5459	484.2766	V	593.3657	297.1865	576.3392	288.6732			5
10	1148.6198	574.8135	1131.5932	566.3002	1130.6092	565.8082	Y	494.2973	247.6523	477.2708	239.1390			4
11	1219.6569	610.3321	1202.6303	601.8188	1201.6463	601.3268	A	331.2340	166.1206	314.2074	157.6074			3
12	1332.7409	666.8741	1315.7144	658.3608	1314.7304	657.8688	L	260.1969	130.6021	243.1703	122.0888			2
13							K	147.1128	74.0600	130.0863	65.5468			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [KTVTSLDVVYALK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
83.6	1477.8392	0.0008	KTVTSLDVVYALK
22.0	1477.8405	-0.0006	DKVTAWKQYRK
18.0	1477.8405	-0.0005	SRKSYPPVYRK
17.9	1477.8405	-0.0006	SRKSYPPVYRK
16.9	1477.8405	-0.0005	SRKSYPPVYRK
15.3	1477.8405	-0.0006	DKVTAWKQYRK
14.8	1477.8405	-0.0006	DKVTAWKQYRK
14.6	1477.8381	0.0018	KTAKTPSKKRK
14.4	1477.8381	0.0018	RLSTISNKLPKK
13.3	1477.8381	0.0018	KTAKTPSKKRK

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>

MATRIX SCIENCE Mascot Search Results

Peptide View

MS/MS Fragmentation of **TVTSLDVVYALK**

Found in **H4_YEAST** in **S_cerevisiae_D**, sp|P02309|H4_YEAST Histone H4 OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae (strain ATCC 204508 / S288c) GN=HHF1 PE=1 SV=2

Match to Query 74388: 1349.744548 from(675.879550,2+) intensity(6512.7119) scans(9988) rawscans(sn9988)

rtinseconds(2994.029) index(131981)

Title: 8500: Scan 9988 (rt=49.9005) [D:\MSData\All\VELOS25424.raw]

Data file D:\Data\MGF\531 Final H4 yeast classical PTMs\mascot_daemon_merge.mgf

Navigation icons: ? Home Search Back Forward 101.18 to 1262.75

Label all possible matches Label matches used for scoring

Monoisotopic mass of neutral peptide Mr(calc): 1349.7442
Fixed modifications: Carbamidomethyl (C) (apply to specified residues or termini only)
Variable modifications:
 K12 : Acetyl (K)
Ions Score: 23 **Expect:** 0.14
Matches : 21/98 fragment ions using 57 most intense peaks ([help](#))

#	b	b ⁺⁺	b ⁰	b ⁰⁺⁺	Seq.	y	y ⁺⁺	y*	y ^{*++}	y ⁰	y ⁰⁺⁺	#
1	102.0550	51.5311	84.0444	42.5258	T							12
2	201.1234	101.0653	183.1128	92.0600	V	1249.7038	625.3556	1232.6773	616.8423	1231.6933	616.3503	11
3	302.1710	151.5892	284.1605	142.5839	T	1150.6354	575.8213	1133.6089	567.3081	1132.6249	566.8161	10
4	389.2031	195.1052	371.1925	186.0999	S	1049.5877	525.2975	1032.5612	516.7842	1031.5772	516.2922	9
5	502.2871	251.6472	484.2766	242.6419	L	962.5557	481.7815	945.5292	473.2682	944.5451	472.7762	8
6	617.3141	309.1607	599.3035	300.1554	D	849.4716	425.2395	832.4451	416.7262	831.4611	416.2342	7
7	716.3825	358.6949	698.3719	349.6896	V	734.4447	367.7260	717.4182	359.2127			6
8	815.4509	408.2291	797.4403	399.2238	V	635.3763	318.1918	618.3497	309.6785			5
9	978.5142	489.7608	960.5037	480.7555	Y	536.3079	268.6576	519.2813	260.1443			4
10	1049.5514	525.2793	1031.5408	516.2740	A	373.2445	187.1259	356.2180	178.6126			3
11	1162.6354	581.8213	1144.6249	572.8161	L	302.2074	151.6074	285.1809	143.0941			2
12					K	189.1234	95.0653	172.0968	86.5520			1

NCBI **BLAST** search of [TVTSLDVVYALK](#)

(Parameters: blastp, nr protein database, expect=20000, no filter, PAM30)

Other BLAST [web gateways](#)

All matches to this query

Score	Mr(calc)	Delta	Sequence
22.7	1349.7442	0.0003	TVTSLDVVYALK
12.8	1349.7415	0.0030	KRRFSTGESLK
10.1	1349.7431	0.0014	SPRTAKKAEIK
9.0	1349.7455	-0.0010	RFANWSSISIK
8.7	1349.7431	0.0014	SPRTAKKAEIK
8.5	1349.7393	0.0052	MPLTTKPLSLK
8.5	1349.7393	0.0052	MPLTTKPLSLK
7.8	1349.7431	0.0014	SIVLRKSNKK
7.8	1349.7431	0.0014	SIVLRKSNKK
6.4	1349.7402	0.0044	TSSITSSKKSLK

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